

An Expression A Day

AEAD PDF Book

No. 601-700 / 100 entries

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Silly / Trivial / Not worth much

くだ
下らない

Kudaranai

silly / trivial / not worth much

Variants

- くだ はなし
下らない話
a silly story
- くだ わら
下らないことで笑う
to laugh at something silly
- くだ おもしろ
下らないけど面白い
silly but funny
- と た
取るに足らない
not worth taking seriously

Adjusted Expression

あまり価値がありません。

It does not have much value.

Example

A 「この映画、^{えいが}下^{くだ}らないよね」 B 「うん、でも、その^{くだ}下^{くだ}らなさがいいんじゃない」

A: This movie is silly, isn't it? B: Yeah, but isn't that silliness what makes it good?

Notes

"Kudaranai" is used when the speaker feels that something has little value or importance. In this example, A calls the movie "kudaranai," but B receives its "kudaranasa" as part of what makes it enjoyable. The suffix "-sa" attaches to an adjective stem and nominalizes the quality or degree expressed by the adjective. Here, by turning "kudaranai" into "kudaranasa," B treats that very silliness as a positive quality of the movie. For this reason, "kudaranai" can be a strong negative evaluation, but it can also express light humor, absurdity, or easy-going fun. When directed at someone's idea or work, it can sound rude, so it should be used with care. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It does not have much value" or "It cannot be considered highly valuable."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

negative evaluation

low value

lightness

humor

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negative evaluation

value judgment

humor

downplaying

Not really / Not very much

あんまり...ない

Anmari ... nai

not really / not very much

Variants

- あまり...ない
not really ...
- そんなに...ない
not that much ...
- それほど...ない
not to that extent ...
- あんまり
not really

Adjusted Expression

あまり...ません。

not very ...

Example

A 「料理^{りょうり}、する？」 B 「うーん、あんまり」

A: Do you cook? B: Hmm, not really.

Notes

"Anmari ... nai" is a colloquial negative expression used when the degree or frequency of something is not high. In this example, B is asked "Do you cook?" and answers only "anmari." Even without saying the rest, "shinai" (I don't), the meaning "I don't cook much" is understood from the previous question. "Anmari" does not make a strong denial; it softens the negative response. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "amari ... masen" (not very ...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

softening negation

expression of degree

moderation of evaluation

elliptical response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negative expression

degree expression

elliptical response

Hardly ever / Almost not

ほとんど...ない

Hotondo ... nai

hardly ever / almost not

Variants

- ほぼ...ない
almost not ...
- めったに...ない
hardly ever ...
- ほとんど...しない
almost never ...
- ほとんど...ありません
there is almost no ...

Adjusted Expression

ほとんど...ません。

hardly ever ... / almost no ...

Example

A 「週末、遊びに行く？」 B 「うーん、ほとんど行かない」

A: Do you go out on weekends? B: Hmm, I hardly ever go out.

Notes

"Hotondo ... nai" is a negative expression used when the frequency, amount, or degree of something is very small, close to zero. In this example, B is asked whether they go out on weekends and answers "hotondo ikanai," meaning that they hardly ever go out. Compared with No.602 "anmari ... nai," which works as a softer negative expression, "hotondo ... nai" is stronger and suggests that the action almost never happens or that there is almost none of something. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "hotondo ... masen" (hardly ever ... / almost no ...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis on negation

expression of frequency

expression of degree

expressing near zero

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negative expression

frequency expression

degree expression

near zero

Regardless of ... / Whether ... or not

～とか^{かんけい}関係なく、

...*toka kankei naku,*

regardless of ... / whether ... or not

Variants

- ～とか^{かんけい}関係なく
regardless of ...
- ～とか^き気にしなくて
without worrying about ...
- ～とか^{もんだい}問題にしないで
without making ... an issue
- ～とか^{かんけい}関係なしに
without regard to ...

Adjusted Expression

～などを^と問わず、

regardless of ...

Example

A 「ラグビー^{らぐびー}って、天気^{てんき}とか^{かんけい}関係なく、試合^{しあい}するの？」 B 「ああ、雨^{あめ}でもやるよ。うん、^{かんけい}関係なくね」

A: In rugby, do they play games regardless of the weather? B: Yeah, they play even in the rain. The weather doesn't really matter.

Notes

"...toka kankei naku" is a spoken expression used when a condition or factor is not treated as relevant to an action or judgment. In this example, A asks whether rugby games are played regardless of the weather, and B answers that they play even in the rain. "Tenki toka kankei naku" means that the weather is not treated as a condition or deciding factor. It is not "toka" alone that means "regardless of"; the whole expression "...toka kankei naku" works as a unit. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "tenkou o towazu" (regardless of the weather) or "...nado o towazu" (regardless of ...).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

removing a condition

denial of influence

taking something out of consideration

confirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

ignoring conditions

denial of influence

confirmation

I told you...

って言ったのに

Tte itta no ni

I told you... / I told you so...

Variants

- って言ったじゃん
I told you, didn't I?
- って言ったでしょ
I told you, right?
- って言ったのにさ
I told you so, you know.

Adjusted Expression

さき^{さき}ほどお伝え^{つた}しました。

I mentioned that earlier.

Example

A 「忘れ^{わす}物^{もの}しちゃった」 B 「だから、忘れ^{わす}るよって言ったのに」

A: I forgot it. B: That's why I told you you'd forget it.

Notes

"Tte itta no ni" is a spoken expression used when the speaker had already given a warning or prediction, but the other person did not take it in and the problem actually happened. In this example, B had already said that

A might forget it, and when A does forget it, B reacts with "wasureru yo tte itta no ni." The "no ni" adds the feeling of dissatisfaction: I told you, but it still happened, or you did not listen. Because it can easily sound reproachful, it should be used with care. Except when used jokingly with someone close, in formal contexts it can be replaced with expressions such as "I mentioned that earlier" or "As I said earlier."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of dissatisfaction reproach restating a warning reaction to a result

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language expression of dissatisfaction reproach
restating a warning

I ended up going that way

そっちに行っちゃった^い

Socchi ni icchatta

I ended up going that way

Variants

- そっちに行っちゃったんだよね^い
I ended up going that way
- そっちに行っちゃったよ^い
I accidentally went that way
- そっちに行っちゃったんだ^い
I drifted in that direction
- 話がそっちに行っちゃった^{はなし い}
The conversation went that way

Adjusted Expression

話がそちらに逸れてしまいました。^{はなし そ}

The conversation has drifted in that direction.

Example

A 「猫が好きなんですねぇ」^{ねこ す} B 「何の話だったっけ？ また、そっちに行っちゃった」^{なん はなし い}

A: So you like cats. B: What were we talking about again? I drifted that way again.

Notes

"Socchi ni icchatta" is a colloquial expression used when the topic or attention has drifted away from the original direction. In this example, B loses track of what they were talking about and says "mata, socchi ni icchatta," noticing that the conversation has gone in another direction again. "Socchi" can refer not only to a physical direction, but also to the direction of a topic, interest, or thought. The "chatta" ending adds the feeling that it happened unintentionally or despite the speaker's intention. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with "The conversation has drifted in that direction."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of result

explanation of an unexpected development

topic drift

self-correction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of result

topic drift

self-correction

chatta

Long story short

はや はなし
早い話

Hayai hanashi

long story short / to put it briefly

Variants

- ^{はや} ^{はなし} 早い話が
long story short
- ^{てみじか} ^い 手短に言うと
to put it briefly
- ^{よう} 要するに
in short
- ^{かんたん} ^い 簡単に言うと
to say it simply

Adjusted Expression

^{てみじか} ^い 手短に言いますと、

to put it briefly,

Example

A 「^{きのう} ^{かいぎ} ^{なが} 昨日の会議、長かったね」 B 「^{はや} ^{はなし} ^{だれ} ^{しゃちょう} ^{べんとう} ^か うん、早い話、誰かが社長のお弁当を買ってくるってこと？」

A: Yesterday's meeting was long, wasn't it? B: Yeah, long story short, someone has to go buy the president's bento, right?

Notes

"Hayai hanashi" is a spoken expression used when the speaker skips a long explanation or complicated background and states only the conclusion. In this example, B sums up the long meeting as "someone has to go buy the president's bento, right?" It is close to "you suru ni" (in short), but "hayai hanashi" can carry light irony or exasperation when the conclusion is simple or somewhat silly compared with the long process leading up to it. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "to put it briefly" or "to summarize."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of summary

concise explanation

conclusion of a story

presenting the bottom line

light irony

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

summary expression

concise explanation

presenting the bottom line

irony

Doesn't fit / Doesn't suit

あ
合わない

Awanai

doesn't fit / doesn't suit

Variants

- ^{にあ}似合わない
doesn't suit
- ^あ合っていない
doesn't match
- ^{てきせつ}適切でない
is not appropriate
- ^{ちょうしあ}調子が合わない
is out of sync
- ^{ひとあ}あの人とは合わない
I don't get along with that person

Adjusted Expression

^あ合いません。

It does not fit / It does not suit.

Example

A 「この服、なんか^あ合わないよね」 B 「うん、色も柄も^あ合っていないかも」

A: This outfit doesn't really suit me, does it? B: Yeah, the color and the pattern may not really work.

Notes

"Awanai" is used when things, people, situations, or feelings do not match or do not fit well together. In this example, A says "nanka awanai yo ne" about an outfit, expressing that the color, pattern, or overall impression does not feel right. "Awanai" can refer to size not fitting, but it can also refer to atmosphere, taste, style, or compatibility not matching. It is also used for interpersonal compatibility, as in "ano hito to wa awanai" (I do not get along with that person). In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It does not fit," "It is not appropriate," or "The compatibility is not good."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of incompatibility

expression of mismatch

negative evaluation

judgment of compatibility

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of incompatibility

negative evaluation

compatibility

Can you lend me this?

か
貸してくれる？

Kashite kureru?

Can you lend me this?

Variants

- 借してもらえる？
Can you lend it to me?
- 借してくれない？
Could you lend it to me?
- 借してくれるかな
I wonder if you could lend it to me
- 借してください
Please lend it to me

Adjusted Expression

借してください。

Please lend it to me.

Example

A 「これ、借してくれる？」 B 「うん、でも、^{かなら}必ず^{かえ}返してよ」

A: Can you lend me this? B: Yeah, but make sure to return it.

Notes

"Kashite kureru?" is a casual request used when the speaker wants to borrow something from the listener. In this example, A says "kore, kashite kureru?" to ask the listener to lend something. "Kasu" means to lend, and "kureru" shows that the action is directed toward the speaker's side. "Kashite ageru" has the opposite direction: it means that the speaker lends something to someone else. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "Please lend it to me" or "Could I borrow it?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of request

seeking help

expression of familiarity

request to borrow

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

request expression

seeking help

giving-receiving expression

That could work too / That might be an option

そういうのもあるかな

Sou iu no mo aru kana

That could work too / That might be an option

Variants

- そういうこともあるかも
That could be the case
- そういう^{ばあい}場合もあるかな
That might be an option
- そういう^{かんが}^{かた}考え方もあるかな
That way of thinking could work too
- それもありかも
That might work too

Adjusted Expression

そのような^{かんが}^{かた}考え方もありますね。

That could also be considered an option.

Example

A 「この^{はな}花、^{みせさき}店先に^お置くよりも、^{なか}中の方が^{ほう}よくない？」 B 「そうねえ、そういうのもあるかな」

A: Wouldn't it be better to put these flowers inside rather than at the storefront? B: Yeah, that could work too.

Notes

"Sou iu no mo aru kana" is a spoken expression used when the speaker hears someone else's suggestion or idea and accepts it as one possible option. In this example, B responds to the suggestion of putting the flowers inside by saying "sou iu no mo aru kana." The speaker is not strongly agreeing, but is also not rejecting the idea; they are recognizing it as a possibility. The ending "kana" adds the feeling of thinking it over or keeping the judgment somewhat open. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "That way of thinking is also possible."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of possibility

accepting an option

recognition of the situation

tentative agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of possibility

option

tentative agreement

Only this much?

たったこれだけ

Tatta kore dake

only this much / just this much

Variants

- これだけしかない
there's only this much
- これだけしか持^もっていない
I only have this much
- これだけしか残^{のこ}っていない
only this much is left
- たったこれだけ？
only this much?

Adjusted Expression

これだけしかありません。

There is only this much.

Example

A 「はい、お小遣^{こづか}い」 B 「え、たったこれだけ？」

A: Here is your allowance. B: What, only this much?

Notes

"Tatta kore dake" is a spoken expression used when the speaker feels that the amount or number is smaller than expected. In this example, B receives an allowance and reacts with "tatta kore dake?", expressing surprise or dissatisfaction that it is less than expected. "Kore dake" points to the amount, and "tatta" emphasizes how small the speaker feels it is. When used directly in response to someone's kindness or payment, it can sound rude, so it should be used with care. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "There is only this much."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of limitation

emphasis on quantity

expression of surprise

dissatisfaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of limitation

emphasis on quantity

surprise

dissatisfaction

Not that, but...

～じゃなくて、

...janakute,

not that, but...

Variants

- ～ではなくて、
not that, but...
- ～じゃなくてさ、
not that, you know...
- ～というより、
rather than that...
- ～の問題もんだいじゃなくて、
it is not a matter of ...

Adjusted Expression

～ではなく、

not ..., but ...

Example

A 「いいとか、悪いとかわるじゃなくて...」 B 「でも、結局けっきょく、したくないんですよ」

A: It is not about whether it is good or bad... B: But in the end, you just do not want to do it, right?

Notes

"...janakute," is a spoken expression used when the speaker rejects one way of seeing or judging something and shifts the conversation to another perspective. In this example, A says "ii toka, warui toka janakute...", meaning that the issue is not whether it is good or bad. However, B reads the underlying point and says, "But in the end, you just do not want to do it, right?" "Janakute" is not simply a negation; it can signal that the current frame is not the one the speaker wants to use, and that the listener should look at the matter from another angle. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "not ..., but ..." or "it is not a matter of ..."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of negation

emphasis on contrast

introduction of explanation

shifting the axis of evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of negation

emphasis on contrast

shifting the axis of evaluation

Even if ... / Even if one did ...

～たところで

...ta tokoro de

even if ... / even if one did ...

Variants

- ～ても
even if ...
- ～たって
even if one did ...
- ～たとしても
even assuming ...
- ～しても ^{いみ}意味がない
it would not matter even if ...

Adjusted Expression

～たとしても

even if ...

Example

A 「^い言ったところで、^{いみ}意味がない」 B 「^{つた}そうかもしれないけど、^{つた}伝えないと...」

A: Even if I say it, it won't make any difference. B: That may be true, but you still have to tell them...

Notes

"...ta tokoro de" is used when the speaker feels that even if an action is taken, the expected result will not occur or it will not make a meaningful difference. In this example, A says "itta tokoro de, imi ga nai," meaning that even if they say it, the situation will not change. It is close to "...temo" (even if), but "...ta tokoro de" is often followed by a negative conclusion and can carry a sense of resignation or futility. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "even if ..." or "even assuming"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of concession

presentation of condition

negative conclusion

sense of futility

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

concessive expression

condition presentation

negative conclusion

sense of futility

Isn't ... really active these days?

いま げんき
今、...がすごい元気じゃないですか

Ima, ... ga sugoi genki janai desu ka

Isn't ... really active these days?

Variants

- さいきん げんき
● 最近、...がすごく元気ですよ
Lately, ... has been really active, hasn't it?
- さいきん かっぼつ
● 最近、...がとても活発ですよ
Lately, ... has been very lively, hasn't it?
- いま も あ
● 今、...がかなり盛り上がってるじゃないですか
These days, ... is really taking off, isn't it?
- いま いきお
● 今、...がすごく勢いありますよね
Right now, ... has a lot of momentum, doesn't it?

Adjusted Expression

さいきん かっぼつ
最近、...がとても活発です。

Recently, ... has been very active.

Example

A 「いま DTMが、すごい元気じゃないですか」 B 「うん、しろうと かんたん つく 素人でも簡単に作れるからね」

A: DTM is really active these days, isn't it? B: Yeah, because even amateurs can make music easily now.

Notes

"Ima, ... ga sugoi genki janai desu ka" is a spoken expression used when the speaker points out that a field, person, or activity is very active or has strong momentum these days, while inviting the listener to share that recognition. In this example, A presents the idea that DTM is currently very active by saying "sugoi genki janai desu ka." The ending "janai desu ka" is not just a question; it creates a shared premise, suggesting that the listener probably recognizes the same situation. "Sugoi genki" can be used for people, and more casually for fields or activities. In more formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "Recently, ... has been very active."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of confirmation

expression of admiration

reporting a situation

presenting shared background

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

confirmation expression

expression of admiration

phrase said in one breath

shared premise

The reason is...

なんでかと言^いうと、

Nande ka to iu to,

the reason is...

Variants

- なんでかと言^いうと、
The reason is, ...
- なぜかと言^いうと、
Why that is, ...
- なんで...かと言^いうと、
The reason why ... is, ...
- ...の理^り由^{ゆう}は、
The reason for ... is, ...

Adjusted Expression

...の理^り由^{ゆう}は、

The reason for ... is, ...

Example

A 「最近^{さいきん}、元^{げん}気^きがないね」 B 「なんでかと言^いうと、仕^し事^{ごと}が忙^いしくて...」

A: You haven't seemed very energetic lately. B: The reason is, I've been busy with work...

Notes

"Nande ka to iu to" is a spoken expression used when the speaker is about to explain the reason or background for their state, judgment, or situation. In this example, B is told that they have not seemed energetic lately and begins the explanation with "nande ka to iu to," saying that they have been busy with work. "Nande" is more casual than "naze" (why), and "ka to iu to" creates a lead-in to the reason that follows. It is a little more orderly than No.554 "naze kattsuu to." In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "The reason is" or "If I may explain why."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

introduction of explanation

presentation of reason

explanation of background

self-explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

introduction of explanation

presentation of reason

background explanation

No, that's not necessarily the case.

いや、そうとは^{かぎ}限らないよ。

Iya, sou to wa kagiranai yo.

No, that's not necessarily the case.

Variants

- いや、^{かなら}必ずしもそうではないよ。
No, that's not always the case.
- いや、^{いちがい}一概にそうとは^い言えないよ。
No, you can't say that across the board.
- いや、^{かぎ}そうとも限らないよ。
No, that may not necessarily be true.
- いや、^いそうとは^き言い切れないよ。
No, you can't say that for sure.

Adjusted Expression

いいえ、^{かぎ}そうとは限りません。

No, that is not necessarily the case.

Example

A 「^{ひと}だいたいの人^{おも}がこれでいいと思っている」 B 「いや、^{かぎ}そうとは限らないよ。」

A: Most people think this is fine. B: No, that's not necessarily the case.

Notes

"Iya, sou to wa kagiranai yo" is a spoken expression used to respond to someone's opinion or generalization by saying that it is not necessarily true. In this example, A says that most people think this is fine, and B replies "sou to wa kagiranai yo," showing that there may be exceptions or other possibilities. The opening "iya" makes the countering move clear, but "sou to wa kagiranai" is not a total denial; it holds back the generalization. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "No, that is not necessarily the case" or "It cannot be said across the board."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of negation

presentation of counterargument

holding back a generalization

presentation of exceptions

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negative expression

presentation of counterargument

holding back a generalization

That's that, and this is this.

それはそれ、これはこれ

Sore wa sore, kore wa kore.

That's that, and this is this.

Variants

- それとこれは別物だよ
That's a separate matter.
- それはそれ、これは別だよ
That and this are different things.
- それぞれ別の話だよ
Let's keep those separate.
- それは関係ないよ
That has nothing to do with this.

Adjusted Expression

それらは別の事柄として扱うべきです。

They should be treated as separate matters.

Example

A 「さっきも僕が払ったんだから、いっしょに払うよ」 B 「ちがう、それはそれ、これはこれ」

A: I already paid earlier, so I'll pay this time too. B: No, that's a separate matter.

Notes

"Sore wa sore, kore wa kore" is a spoken expression used when the speaker treats two matters separately instead of mixing them together. In this example, A says that since he paid earlier, he will pay this time too, but B replies "sore wa sore, kore wa kore," separating the earlier payment from the present one. It does not simply mean that two things are different; it also draws a line so that one matter is not used as the reason for handling the other. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "They should be treated as separate matters" or "That and this are separate issues."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of distinction emphasis on independence presentation of contrast

drawing a line between matters

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language expression of distinction presentation of contrast

drawing a line separate matter

Even if you say that.

そんなこと言^いったって。

Sonna koto itta tte.

Even if you say that.

Variants

- そう言^いわれても。
Even if you say that.
- そんなことを言^いわれても。
Even if you tell me that.
- そうは言^いっても。
That may be true, but...
- そんなこと言^いったってさ。
You can say that, but...

Adjusted Expression

そう言^いわれましても、

Even if you say that,

Example

A 「彼は^{かれ}本当に^{ほんとう}忙しい^{いそが}んだよ」 B 「そんなこと言^いったって、約束^{やくそく}は守^{まも}ってほしい」

A: He is really busy. B: Even if you say that, I still want him to keep his promise.

Notes

"Sonna koto itta tte" is a spoken expression used when the speaker hears the other person's explanation or excuse but still feels that it does not resolve their complaint or demand. In this example, A gives the reason that he is very busy, but B replies "sonna koto itta tte," showing that even if he is busy, B still wants him to keep his promise. The speaker is not completely ignoring the reason, but is saying that the reason is not enough to make them accept the situation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "Even if you say that" or "Even if you put it that way."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of concession presentation of counterargument expression of dissatisfaction

not accepting the reason as sufficient

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language concessive expression

presentation of counterargument expression of dissatisfaction

not accepting the reason as sufficient

That's not true.

そんなことないよ。

Sonna koto nai yo.

That's not true.

Variants

- そうじゃないよ。
That's not true.
- そんなことはないよ。
That's not the case.
- そういうわけではないよ。
That's not how it is.
- いや、そんなことないよ。
No, that's not true.

Adjusted Expression

そうではありません。

That is not the case.

Example

A 「^{かれ}彼は^{ほんとう}本当に^{いそが}忙しいんだよ」 B 「^きそんなことないよ、^{きのう}昨日も^{あそ}遊んでたじゃない」

A: He is really busy. B: That's not true. He was hanging out yesterday too.

Notes

"Sonna koto nai yo" is a spoken expression used to directly deny what someone has said or how they see the situation. In this example, A says that he is really busy, but B replies "sonna koto nai yo" and denies that explanation by pointing out that he was hanging out yesterday too. Compared with No.618 "sonna koto itta tte," which accepts that the other person has given a reason but says that the reason is not enough, "sonna koto nai yo" denies the claim itself. It is natural in close conversation, but if said strongly, it can sound like a direct rejection of the other person's view. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "That is not the case" or "It cannot be said that way."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of negation

presentation of counterargument

difference of opinion

correcting the other person's view

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negative expression

presentation of counterargument

correcting perception

It's not just about being usable or working

つか
使えればいい、^{うご}動けばいいっていうんじ
ゃなくて、

Tsukaereba ii, ugokeba ii tte iu n janakute,

It's not just about being usable or working

Variants

- ^{つか}使えればいいとか、^{うご}動けばいいとかじゃなくて、
It's not just about being usable or working
- ^{つか}使えるだけでなく、^{つか}使いやすさも^{だいじ}大事で、
It's not just about whether it can be used or whether it works
- ^{うご}動くことだけが^{だいじ}大事なんじゃなくて、
It isn't only that it works
- ^{さいていげんつか}最低限使えるだけではなくて、
It's not enough that it is minimally usable

Adjusted Expression

^{つか}使えることや^{うご}動くことだけが^{じゅうよう}重要なものではありません。

It is not only important that it can be used or that it works.

Example

A 「この^{そふと}ソフト、^{つか}使えればいい、^{うご}動けばいいっていうんじゃなくて、^{つか}使いやす
さも^{じゅうし}重視してほしい」 B 「そうだね、^み見た目も^め大事^{だいじ}だよ」

A: With this software, it's not just about being usable or working. I also want ease of use to matter. B: Right. The way it looks matters too.

Notes

"Tsukaereba ii, ugokeba ii tte iu n janakute" is a spoken expression used when the speaker says that merely being usable or working is not enough and shifts the discussion to another standard of value. In this example, A says that for this software, it is not enough that it can be used or that it works; ease of use should also matter. The speaker first quotes the low standard "tsukaereba ii" and "ugokeba ii," then rejects it with "tte iu n janakute," creating another axis of evaluation such as quality, usability, or appearance. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It is not only important that it can be used or that it works."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of values

emphasis on quality

rejection of the minimum condition

shifting the axis of evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of values

emphasis on quality

rejecting the minimum condition

shifting the axis of evaluation

No, that's...

いや、それは...

Iya, sore wa...

No, that's...

Variants

- いや、それはちょっと...
No, that's a bit...
- いや、それはなんて言え^いばいいか...
No, how should I put this...
- いや、それはねえ...
No, well, that's...
- いや、そこまでしていただくのは...
No, I couldn't ask you to go that far...

Adjusted Expression

恐縮^{きょうしゆく}ですが、それはお受け取り^{うけとり}できません。

I am sorry, but I cannot accept that.

Example

A 「これ、先日^{せんじつ}のお礼^{れい}です」 B 「いや、それは...」

A: This is a thank you for the other day. B: No, that's...

Notes

"Iya, sore wa..." is an incomplete spoken expression used when the speaker finds it difficult to accept someone's offer or action directly, and shows apology or hesitation before giving a clear refusal. In this example, B is offered a gift of thanks and stops with "iya, sore wa..." instead of either accepting it immediately or clearly refusing it. At this point, the interaction already works: B acknowledges the other person's kindness while showing hesitation about accepting it as it is. The unfinished form itself does important work. In formal contexts, if the speaker needs to be explicit, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I am sorry, but I cannot accept that."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

avoiding a direct response

expressing an apologetic stance

maintaining interpersonal harmony

showing difficulty in accepting

trailing off

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

negative expression

hesitation expression

trailing off

incomplete sentence

Easily / Without difficulty

やすやす
易々と

Yasuyasu to

easily / without difficulty

Variants

• かんたん簡単に

easily

• たやすく

without difficulty

• なん難なく

with ease

• まんまと

just like that

Adjusted Expression

かんたん簡単に

easily

Example

A 「これはなかなかこわ壊れませんよ」 B 「そうやすやす易々とだま騙されるもんか」

A: This is quite durable. B: I won't be fooled that easily.

Notes

"Yasuyasu to" means easily or without difficulty. It does not mean cheaply in terms of price. In this example, B does not immediately believe the other person's explanation and says "sou yasuyasu to damasareru mon ka," meaning "I won't be fooled that easily." While "yasuyasu to" can simply mean "easily," it often appears in expressions involving caution or resistance, such as being deceived easily, backing down easily, or handing something over easily, especially in negative forms. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "easily" or "without difficulty."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

ease

caution

denial of giving in easily

refusal to be deceived

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

ease

caution

refusal to be deceived

For me / Personally

ぼく^{てき}的には、

Boku teki ni wa,

for me / personally

Variants

- わたし^{てき}的には、
For me,
- おれ^{てき}的には、
Personally,
- あたし^{てき}的には、
From my perspective,
- 個人^{こじんてき}的には、
As far as I'm concerned,

Adjusted Expression

個人^{こじんてき}的には、

Personally,

Example

A 「この映画、面白^{えいが おもしろ}かった？」 B 「ぼく^{てき}的には、あまり良^よくなかったかな」

A: Did you enjoy this movie? B: Personally, I didn't think it was very good.

Notes

"Boku teki ni wa" is a casual spoken expression used to mark what follows as the speaker's own subjective opinion. In this example, B says that the movie was not very good, but by adding "boku teki ni wa," the speaker shows that this is not a general evaluation, but their own personal impression. The pattern "X teki ni wa" attaches to a noun and creates a temporary standpoint or perspective. It is now also commonly used with people or organizations, as in "Nakamura-kun teki ni wa, dou omou no?" (How do you see it, Nakamura?) or "kaisha teki ni wa" (from the company's standpoint). However, expressions such as "boku teki ni wa" and "Nakamura-kun teki ni wa" are casual spoken forms. In formal contexts, they can be replaced with expressions such as "personally," "in Mr. Nakamura's view," or "from the company's standpoint."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of personal opinion

presentation of subjective viewpoint

softening assertion

self-limiting the statement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of opinion

subjective viewpoint

avoiding strong assertion

youth-like expression

Generally speaking / In the eyes of society

よ なかてき
世の中の的には、

Yo no naka teki ni wa,

generally speaking / in the eyes of society

Variants

- ^{しゃかいてき}社会的には、
socially speaking,
- ^{せけんてき}世間的には、
in the eyes of the public,
- ^{いっばんてき}一般的には、
generally speaking,
- ^{よ なか}世の中では、
in society,

Adjusted Expression

^{いっばんてき}
一般的には、

Generally speaking,

Example

A 「この仕事、^{しごと}大変だよね」 B 「うん、世の中の的^{よ なかてき}には、^あ当たり前^{まえ}なんだろうけど」

A: This job is tough, isn't it? B: Yeah, generally speaking, people may think it's normal, though.

Notes

"Yo no naka teki ni wa" is a casual spoken expression used when the speaker refers to how something is generally seen or judged by society. In this example, B feels that the job is tough, but says "yo no naka teki ni wa, atarimae nan darou kedo," putting some distance between their own feeling and what people in general may think. "Yo no naka teki ni wa" does not refer to a clear opinion held by a specific person; rather, it temporarily sets up the vague standpoint of society or the public. Like No.623 "boku teki ni wa," it uses the pattern "X teki ni wa" to create a viewpoint, but here the viewpoint holder is society rather than an individual. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "generally speaking" or "in society at large."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presentation of a societal viewpoint

expression of general perception

sharing of values

distance from one's own feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

societal viewpoint

general perception

X teki ni wa

distancing

Huh, isn't that the kind of thing I like?

え、それ、^{ぼく} ^す僕の好きなやつじゃないですか。

E, sore, boku no suki na yatsu janai desu ka.

Huh, isn't that the kind of thing I like?

Variants

- あれ、それ、^{わたし} ^す私の好きなやつじゃないですか。
Huh, isn't that the kind of thing I like?
- おお、それ、^{おれ} ^す俺の好きなやつじゃないですか。
Oh, isn't that exactly my kind of thing?
- うわ、それ、^すあたしの好きなやつじゃないですか。
Wow, that's the kind of thing I like.
- え、それ、^{ぼく} ^す僕、好きなやつです。
Huh, I like that kind of thing.

Adjusted Expression

それは^{わたし} ^す私の好きなものです。

That is the kind of thing I like.

Example

A 「これ、^{あた} ^ら新しい^げ ^ー ^むゲームだよ」 B 「え、それ、^{ぼく} ^す僕の好きなやつじゃないですか」

A: This is a new game. B: Huh, isn't that exactly the kind of thing I like?

Notes

"E, sore, boku no suki na yatsu janai desu ka" is a spoken expression used when the speaker sees something presented by the other person and reacts by recognizing that it matches their own taste. In this example, B sees the new game and says "boku no suki na yatsu janai desu ka," expressing both surprise and pleasure. "Yatsu" here does not refer to a person; it casually refers to a thing or type of thing. "Janai desu ka" is not just a question; it creates the feeling that the listener can share or recognize the speaker's reaction. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "That is the kind of thing I like" or "That suits my taste."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of surprise

expression of joy

recognizing one's preference

presenting a shared premise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of surprise

expression of joy

preference

janai desu ka

You got a good one, didn't you?

いいの^げ^っ^とゲットしたね。

Ii no getto shita ne.

You got a good one, didn't you?

Variants

- いいものを^て手に^い入れたね
You got a good one, didn't you?
- いい^{しな}品^かを買ったね
You got a good item, didn't you?
- いい^{もの}物を^て手に^い入れたね
You bought a good product, didn't you?
- いいの^か買ったね
You bought a nice one, didn't you?

Adjusted Expression

いいものを^て手に^い入れましたね。

You obtained a good item, didn't you?

Example

A 「これ、^{あたら}新しい^きキー^ぼボード^どだよ」 B 「いいの^げ^っ^とゲットしたね」

A: This is my new keyboard. B: You got a good one, didn't you?

Notes

"Ii no getto shita ne" is a casual spoken expression used when the speaker notices that the listener has obtained something good and responds with praise or shared pleasure. In this example, B sees the listener's new keyboard and reacts positively by saying "ii no getto shita ne." "Ii no" is a casual form meaning "a good one," and "getto shita" is a very casual way to say "got," "obtained," or "bought." The expression does not simply recognize the listener's possession; it also suggests "You chose a good one" or "Good for you." In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "You obtained a good item, didn't you?"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of praise

positive evaluation

reaction to an acquisition

sharing the listener's pleasure

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of praise

positive evaluation

casual expression

And... yeah, that's about it

...て、はい、...

...te, hai, ...

and... yeah, that's about it

Variants

- ...して、はい、...
and... yeah, that's about it
- ...やって、はい、...
did this and that, and... yeah
- ...^た食べて、^の飲んで、はい、...
ate and drank, and... yeah
- ...で、はい、...
and, well, that's it

Adjusted Expression

...して、そんなところです。

...and that was about it.

Example

A 「^{きのう}昨日、^{ばーてい}パーティ、どうだった？」 B 「まあ、^た食べて^の飲んで、はい、」 A 「い
つも^{おな}と同じかあ」

A: How was the party yesterday? B: Well, we ate and drank, and... yeah, that's about it. A: Same as always, huh?

Notes

"...te, hai, ..." is a spoken trailing-off pattern used after listing actions, when the speaker has nothing much more to add and hands the conversation back to the listener. In this example, B says "tabete nonde, hai," meaning that they ate and drank, and that was about it. "Hai" here is not an answer of "yes"; it works more like an interjection that wraps up the talk and lets the listener take it. The utterance is incomplete as a sentence, but that incompleteness itself helps end the explanation and pass the turn. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "...and that was about it."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

continuation of conversation

ending a list

handing the conversation over

wrapping up an explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

conversation continuation

trailing-off expression

incomplete expression

handover in conversation

This might actually be good

なんか、^い良いかも

Nanka, ii kamo.

This might actually be good / I kind of like it

Variants

- なんとなく、^い良いかもしれない
This might actually be good
- なんだか、^い良いかもね
I kind of like it
- なんとなく、^い良^き気がする
Somehow, I feel it might be good
- なんか、^す好きかも
I might like this

Adjusted Expression

なんとなく、^よ良いかもしれません。

It may be good.

Example

A 「このヘッドホン、どう？」 B 「うん、なんか、^い良いかも」

A: How about these headphones? B: Yeah, I kind of like them.

Notes

"Nanka, ii kamo" is a spoken expression used when the speaker feels a positive possibility about something, even though they cannot yet clearly explain why. In this example, B tries the headphones and says "nanka, ii kamo," showing a favorable impression while the evaluation is still forming. "Nanka" signals a vague feeling whose reason has not yet been articulated, and "kamo" avoids a firm assertion and presents the judgment as a possibility. For this reason, the expression can leave the evaluation open and invite the listener's response or further opinion. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "It may be good" or "I have a favorable impression."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of positive possibility

sharing of vague feelings

presentation of evaluation in progress

prompting the listener's response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of affirmation

expression of possibility

vague expression

trailing-off expression

evaluation in progress

Either is fine

どちらでも、

Dochira demo,

Either is fine / I'm fine with either

Variants

- どちらでもいいです
Either is fine
- どっちでもいいよ
I'm fine with either
- どちらにしても大丈夫だいじょうぶです
Either way is okay
- どちらでも構かまいません
Whichever you prefer is fine

Adjusted Expression

どちらでも結構けっこうです。

Either is fine.

Example

A 「お昼は和食わしょく? 洋食ようしょく?」 B 「どちらでも、」

A: For lunch, Japanese food or Western food? B: I'm fine with either.

Notes

"Dochira demo," is a spoken trailing-off expression used to show that either of two options is acceptable and to leave the choice to the listener. In this example, B shows that either Japanese food or Western food is fine, leaving room for the other person to decide. A fuller form would be "dochira demo ii desu" (either is fine), but by stopping at "dochira demo," the speaker naturally conveys that they do not have a strong preference and can go along with the listener's choice. Depending on the situation, however, it may also sound as if the speaker is avoiding making a decision. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "Either is fine" or "Either is acceptable."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presentation of freedom of choice

expression of neutral stance

suggestion of flexible response

leaving the choice to the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of choice

expression of neutrality

expression of flexibility

trailing-off

There's no other choice.

それしかない。

Sore shika nai.

There's no other choice.

Variants

- ほか せんたくし他に選択肢がない。
There's no other choice.
- いがい ほうほうこれ以外に方法がない。
There are no other options.
- いがい せんたくしこれ以外の選択肢はない。
There's no alternative.
- もうそれしかない。
That's the only option left.

Adjusted Expression

ほか せんたくし他に選択肢がありません。

There are no other options.

Example

A 「この問題、どうする？ やめる？」 B 「うーん、それしかない」

A: What should we do about this problem? Quit? B: Hmm, there's no other choice.

Notes

"Sore shika nai" is a spoken expression used when the speaker judges that no other option remains. In this example, A suggests quitting as a way to deal with the problem, and B answers "sore shika nai," accepting that there is no method other than quitting. "Shika nai" limits the choice to one option and closes off other possibilities. It can express a firm decision, but it can also carry resignation, as if the speaker has no choice but to accept the situation. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "There are no other options" or "There is no other method."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of lack of options

emphasis on decision

acceptance of the situation

resignation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of lack of options

emphasis on decision

acceptance of the situation

resignation

I'm not so sure about that.

それ、どうだろ？

Sore, dou daro?

I'm not so sure about that.

Variants

- それ、どうかな？
I'm not so sure about that.
- それ、どうなんだろう？
I wonder if that's really true.
- それはどうだろうね
I'm not sure that will work.
- うーん、それはどうかな
Hmm, I don't know about that.

Adjusted Expression

それについては、やや疑問ぎもんがあります。

I have some doubts about that.

Example

A 「この計画けいかく、成功せいこうするよ」 B 「それ、どうだろ？」

A: This plan will succeed. B: I'm not so sure about that.

Notes

"Sore, dou daro?" is a spoken expression used when the speaker has some doubt about what the other person has said or judged. In this example, A states that the plan will succeed, but B replies "sore, dou daro?" showing that they are not ready to accept that conclusion. "Dou daro" does not strongly deny the claim; it holds back judgment and gently introduces doubt. It can also be used to ask for someone's opinion, but in this example its main function is to softly stop the other person's assertion. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I have some doubts about that" or "It cannot be said for certain that it will succeed."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of doubt

suggestion of uncertainty

soft disagreement

holding back from accepting an assertion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken language

expression of doubt

uncertainty

soft disagreement

holding back an assertion

No one would know the answer.

わかる^{ひと}人なんて誰^{だれ}もいない。

Wakaru hito nante dare mo inai.

No one would know the answer.

Variants

- わかる^{ひと}人なんて誰^{だれ}もいません。

No one would know the answer.

- 答^{こた}えが分^わかる人^{ひと}なんて誰^{だれ}もいない。

There's no one who knows the answer.

- 理^り解^{かい}できる人^{ひと}なんて誰^{だれ}もいない。

No one can understand this.

- こんな^わの分^わかる人^{ひと}いないよ。

No one would be able to figure this out.

Adjusted Expression

答^{こた}えが分^わかる人^{ひと}はいないと思^{おも}います。

I do not think anyone knows the answer.

Example

A 「この問題^{もんだい}、できる？」 B 「これは難^{むずか}しいよ。わかる人^{ひと}なんて誰^{だれ}もいないよ」

A: Can you solve this problem? B: This is hard. No one would know the answer.

Notes

"Wakaru hito nante dare mo inai" is a spoken expression used when the speaker feels that a problem or content is so difficult that no one would understand it or know the answer. In this example, B looks at the problem and says "wakaru hito nante dare mo inai yo," judging that it is too difficult for ordinary people to solve. "Dare mo inai" is a total negation, and "nante" adds the feeling that it is hard to even imagine such a person existing. In formal contexts, it can be replaced with expressions such as "I do not think anyone knows the answer" or "I think very few people would understand it."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of difficulty in understanding denial of possibility

emphasis on shared recognition strong estimation

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken language difficulty in understanding denial of possibility

shared recognition nante

So, do you have anything?

じゃあ、なんかありますか？

Jaa, nanka arimasu?

So, do you have anything?

Variants

- じゃあ、他にありますか？
So, do you have anything?
- じゃあ、何かありますか？
Well then, is there anything else?
- じゃあ、ほかに何かありますか？
So, do you have any other options?

Adjusted Expression

では、^{ほか} ^{なに}他に何かありますか？

Well then, is there anything else?

Example

A 「これはあまりよくないよ」 B 「じゃあ、なんかありますか？」

A: This one isn't very good. B: So, do you have anything?

Notes

'Jaa, nanka arimasu?' is used after the other person has rejected or criticized the current option, and the speaker asks for another suggestion or possibility. 'Jaa' makes the utterance arise as the next reaction to the other person's negative comment. Although 'arimasu?' is polite in form,

'nanka arimasu?' is not a fully adjusted request like 'Do you have any good suggestions?'. It hands the next move back to the listener. Depending on the situation, it can sound not only like a neutral check but also like mild pushback: if this is no good, then what else do you have?

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

prompting additional suggestions

checking available options

mild pushback

continuation of conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

additional suggestion

option confirmation

pushback

Do you have time?

じかん
時間、ある？

Jikan aru?

Do you have time?

Variants

- ^{じかん}時間、ありますか？
Do you have time?
- ^{ひま}暇、ありますか？
Are you free?
- ^{じかん}時間、^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫ですか？
Is now okay for you?

Adjusted Expression

^{いま}今、^{すこ}少し^{じかん}お時間よろしいでしょうか？

Do you have a moment now?

Example

A 「^{いま}今、^{じかん}時間、ある？」 B 「うん、いいよ」

A: Do you have time now? B: Yeah, sure.

Notes

'Jikan aru?' does not simply ask whether the listener possesses time. It opens the possibility of talking, asking for something, or starting a consultation. The noun 'jikan' is presented first, and 'aru?' immediately

checks the listener's availability, making the expression short and highly immediate. The reply 'Un, ii yo' does not only mean that the listener has time. It also means that the speaker may begin: you can talk, you can ask, or you can start.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking availability

checking the listener's convenience

initiation of conversation

opening a request or topic

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

time check

availability check

conversation opener

Still mulling it over

やや、^{なや}悩んでる、

Yaya, nayanderu,

Still mulling it over,

Variants

- ちょっと、^{なや}悩んでる、
Still thinking about it,
- ^{すこ}少し、^{なや}悩んでる、
Still mulling it over,
- まあ、^{なや}悩んでる、
Still not sure,
- I'm going to sleep on it.

Adjusted Expression

まだ^{けんとう}検討しているところです。

I'm still considering it.

Example

A 「この^{ていあん}提案、どうする？」 B 「やや、^{なや}悩んでる、」

A: What should we do about this proposal? B: Still mulling it over, ...

Notes

'Yaya, nayanderu,' is not mainly a statement of deep emotional distress. It shows the listener that the speaker has not yet reached a decision. Compared with 'chotto,' 'yaya' sounds somewhat more formal or self-observing in ordinary conversation, and it creates a small distance from the speaker's own hesitation. The speaker is not simply throwing out a worry, but lightly objectifying the current internal processing state: I am still in the middle of deciding. Because the utterance stops at 'nayanderu,' it does not give a conclusion. It hands the unfinished state to the listener as an incomplete sentence.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of thought process

postponement of decision

sharing of introspection

showing an unfinished judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of thought

postponement of decision

incomplete sentence

What I just saw was,

いま み
今、見たのは、

Ima, mita no wa,

What I just saw was,

Variants

- さっき、見たのは、
What I just saw was,
- たったいま、見たのは、
What I saw a moment ago was,
- 今しがた、見たのは、
What I saw just now was,

Adjusted Expression

さき み
先ほど見たものは、

What I saw just now was,

Example

A 「いま、見たのは、何だったの」 B 「あれはながほし」

A: What was that I just saw? B: That was a shooting star.

Notes

'Ima, mita no wa,' brings up something the speaker has just seen and prepares to ask what it was. Here 'ima' means 'just now' or 'a moment ago', not 'recently' in a broad sense. By stopping at 'mita no wa,' the

speaker places the seen object in front of the listener as a noun phrase, while leaving its identity or explanation unfinished. The utterance shares the immediate experience and hands the task of identification to the listener: what was that thing I just saw?

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking what was seen immediate report of an experience

asking the listener to identify something introduction of topic incomplete sentence

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken experience report request for identification

incomplete sentence

I made fish.

さかな つく
魚、作ったよ。

Sakana, tsukutta yo.

I made fish.

Variants

- さかな つく 魚、作りましたよ。

I made fish.

- さかな ちょうり 魚、調理したよ。

I cooked fish.

- さかな りょうり つく 魚の料理、作ったよ。

I made a fish dish.

Adjusted Expression

さかな ちょうり
魚を調理しました。

I cooked fish.

Example

A 「ゆうしょく なに 夕食、何にする？」 B 「さかな つく 魚、作ったよ」

A: What should we have for dinner? B: I made fish.

Notes

'Sakana, tsukutta yo' does not mean that the speaker literally made a fish. It means that the speaker prepared a dish using fish. By putting 'sakana' first as a noun, instead of saying a fully adjusted sentence like 'I cooked

fish,' the speaker immediately presents it as a meal option in response to the question. 'Tsukutta yo' reports not only the completion of cooking, but also the shared availability of the food: it is already prepared, and you can eat it.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reporting what was cooked

presenting a meal

sharing what has been prepared

responding to a meal choice

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

cooking report

meal presentation

noun-first expression

It doesn't click.

びん こ
ピンと来ない。

Pin to konai.

It doesn't click.

Variants

- びん き
ピンと来ません。

It doesn't click.

- こ
しっくり来ない。

It doesn't feel right.

- ちが かん
なんとなく違う感じがする。

It doesn't quite make sense.

-

I don't really get it.

Adjusted Expression

ちよっかんてき なっとく
直感的には納得できません。

It does not feel intuitively convincing to me.

Example

A 「このデザイン、どう思う？」 B 「うーん、びん こピンと来ない」

A: What do you think of this design? B: Hmm, it doesn't click.

Notes

'Pin to konai' does not simply mean that the speaker cannot understand something. The speaker may understand the explanation or see the object, but acceptance, response, or a sense of rightness has not arisen internally. The verb 'konai' presents this as something that has not arrived: the intuitive reaction has not been activated. In evaluating a design, the expression allows the speaker to hand over a vague but immediate mismatch before giving any specific reason.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing intuitive mismatch

sharing a sense of unease

showing that acceptance has not formed

suspending evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of feeling

expression of mismatch

expression of intuition

suspension of evaluation

How have you been?

げんき
元気してる？

Genki shiteru?

How have you been?

Variants

- げんき 元気ですか？

How have you been?

- ちょうし 調子はどう？

How are you?

- さいきん げんき 最近、元気？

How's it going?

Adjusted Expression

おげんき お元気でいらっしゃいますか？

How have you been?

Example

A 「ひさ 久しぶり！げんき 元気してる？」 B 「うん、げんき 元気だよ」

A: Long time no see! How have you been? B: Yeah, I've been fine.

Notes

'Genki shiteru?' does not simply ask about the listener's health. It lightly opens the listener's recent situation, especially when the speaker has not seen them for a while. Here 'genki' combines with 'suru' and appears as

'genki shiteru,' expressing a continuing state. This does not mean that the dictionary-like form 'genki suru' is freely used in ordinary speech. Rather, the expression becomes natural within the conversational chain 'Genki shiteru?' Many Japanese nouns can combine with 'suru' and become suru-verbs, but learners often do not notice that a state noun like 'genki' can appear in this kind of verbal form. After 'Hisashiburi!', it functions as a way to restart contact and gives the listener a place to begin talking about how they have been.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking recent condition

reopening contact with the listener

initiation of conversation

showing concern for the listener's state

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

checking in

conversation opener

expression of concern

Somehow, it's weird.

なんか、^{へん}変。

Nanka, hen.

Somehow, it's weird.

Variants

- なんとなく、^{へん}変。
Somehow, it's weird.
- なんだか、^{へん}変。
Something feels off.
- なんとなく、おかしい。
It feels kind of strange.
- Something's not right.

Adjusted Expression

なんとなく、^{いわかん}違和感があります。

I have a vague sense that something is off.

Example

A 「この^{でざいん}デザイン、どう？」 B 「うーん、なんか、^{へん}変」

A: How about this design? B: Hmm, something feels off.

Notes

'Nanka, hen' shows that a sense of unease has arisen before the speaker can clearly explain the reason. 'Nanka' indicates that the basis of the evaluation has not yet become clear. 'Hen' can be a strong judgment, but with 'nanka' before it, the utterance does not simply reject the object. It shares a felt impression: I cannot yet say why, but something feels off to me. In evaluating a design, it works as an immediate reaction before any specific problem is stated.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of unease

evaluation before reasons are clear

sharing a felt impression

suspension of evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of unease

sharing a felt impression

reason not yet formed

suspension of evaluation

I'm glad I did it.

しといてよかった。

Shitoite yokatta.

I'm glad I did it.

Variants

- やっておいてよかった。
I'm glad I did it.
- しておいてよかった。
I'm glad I took care of it.
- やっといてよかった。
I'm glad I got it done.

Adjusted Expression

しておいて正解せいかいでした。

It was the right thing to do.

Example

A 「これ、最後のさいご一つひと？」 B 「まだあるよ。たくさん買かってよかったね」

A: Is this the last one? B: There are still more. I'm glad we bought a lot.

Notes

'Shitoite yokatta' is used when a past action turns out to have been useful later. 'Shitoite' is a casual form of 'shite oite,' meaning to do something in advance in preparation for a future need. 'Yokatta' reevaluates that past action positively from the present result. In the example 'Kattoite yokatta

ne,' the earlier action of buying a lot is connected to the present relief that there is still enough left.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reevaluating a past action

affirming prior preparation

expression of relief

reaction after seeing the result

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluation of past action

prior preparation

expression of relief

Sorry this is all I can do

これぐらいしかできなくて、

Kore gurai shika dekinakute,

Sorry this is all I can do,

Variants

- これぐらいしかできなくて、
Sorry this is all I can do,
- これだけしかできなくて、
Sorry I can only do this much,
- これぐらいしかできなくて、すみません。
I'm sorry this is all I can do.

Adjusted Expression

これぐらいしかできなくて、もう わけ申し訳ありません。

I'm sorry this is all I can do.

Example

A 「これ、てっだ手伝ってくれてありがとう」 B 「ごめんね、これぐらいしかできなくて」

A: Thank you for helping me with this. B: Sorry this is all I can do.

Notes

'Kore gurai shika dekinakute,' presents what the speaker has done as not quite enough, while expressing apology or hesitation toward the listener. 'Kore gurai' makes the speaker's contribution sound limited, and 'shika

'dekinai' marks that nothing more could be done. Because the utterance stops at 'dekinakute,' the apology is activated even when 'gomen ne' or 'sumimasen' is not explicitly added. In the example, the listener is thanking the speaker, but the speaker still feels that their help may not have been enough and offers that sense of insufficiency first.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting one's contribution as insufficient

expression of apology

sharing one's limitation

showing consideration for the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

apology expression

incomplete sentence

presentation of limitation

shika-nai

Let me do this much

これぐらいはさせて

Kore gurai wa sasete,

Let me do this much

Variants

- これぐらいはさせて
Let me do this much.
- これだけはさせて
Please let me do this much.
- これぐらいはさせてください。
Let me at least do this much, please.

Adjusted Expression

これぐらいは私わたしに任まかせてください。

Please let me handle at least this much.

Example

A 「これ、手てっだ伝だってくれてありがとう」 B 「これぐらいはさせて」

A: Thank you for helping me with this. B: Let me at least do this much.

Notes

'Kore gurai wa sasete' is used when the listener thanks the speaker or hesitates to accept help, and the speaker offers to do at least this much.

'Kore gurai' presents the speaker's action not as a large contribution, but as a small and reasonable one. The particle 'wa' sets a minimum line:

even if I cannot do everything, please let me take care of at least this much. Because the utterance stops at 'sasete,' it does not sound like an order. It remains an incomplete sentence that asks for permission while offering the speaker's willingness.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of an offer

consideration for the listener

presenting a minimum contribution

response to the listener's hesitation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

offer expression

expression of consideration

minimum contribution

incomplete sentence

It doesn't budge at all.

びく
ビクともしない。

Biku to mo shinai.

It doesn't budge at all.

Variants

- まったく うご動かない。

It doesn't budge at all.

- まったく うご動かない。

It doesn't move at all.

- ぜんぜん うご動かない。

It won't move at all.

Adjusted Expression

まったく うご動きません。

It does not move at all.

Example

A 「この どドア、あ開けてみて」 B 「うーん、びくビクともしない」

A: Try opening this door. B: Hmm, it doesn't budge at all.

Notes

'Biku to mo shinai' does not simply mean that something does not move. It means that even after force is applied or someone tries to move it, there is not the slightest response. 'Biku' evokes a tiny movement or

reaction, and 'to mo ... nai' emphasizes that even that minimum reaction does not occur. In the example, the speaker reports the result immediately after trying to open the door: it did not move even a little.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of immobility emphasizing lack of response report after trying
presenting the object's resistance

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of immobility emphatic expression
reaction after trying mimetic expression

That's something different.

それ、^{べつもの}別物。

Sore, betsumono.

That's something different.

Variants

- それ、^{べつもの}別の物。
That's something different.
- それ、^{ちがもの}違う物。
That's a different thing.
- それ、^{べつもの}別物です。
That's a different matter.
- That's not the same thing.

Adjusted Expression

それとは^{べつもの}別の物です。

That is a different thing.

Example

A 「これが、^{いぜん}以前、^{はな}話してたものなの？」 B 「ううん、それ、^{べつもの}別物」

A: Is this what you were talking about before? B: No, that's something different.

Notes

'Sore, betsumono' is used when the listener identifies something with a previous item or another thing, and the speaker cuts that connection and corrects it. 'Betsumono' does not only mean another physical item. It can also mean that even if two things look related or similar, they are qualitatively different and should not be treated as the same. By stopping with the noun 'betsumono,' the speaker immediately cancels the identification before giving any longer explanation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of distinction correcting identification repairing a misunderstanding
presenting a qualitative difference

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of distinction misunderstanding correction
noun-final expression undoing identification

Because I'm a complete amateur,

しろウト
ど素人なんで、...。

Doshirouto nande, ...

Because I'm a complete amateur, ...

Variants

- しろウト
ど素人なんですけど、...

Because I'm a complete amateur, ...

- しろウト
ど素人だから、...

Since I'm a complete amateur, ...

- しろウト
ど素人なので、...

As I'm a total beginner, ...

Adjusted Expression

まったくのしろウトなので、あまりきたい
期待しないでください。

Please don't expect much, as I'm a complete amateur.

Example

A 「このしごと、てっだ
手伝ってくれる？」 B 「ごめんね、しろウト
なんで、あまりやく
役に
た
立てないかも」

A: Can you help me with this work? B: Sorry, I'm a complete amateur, so I might not be much help.

Notes

'Doshirouto nande, ...' is used to show in advance that the speaker is not knowledgeable in the relevant field and to lower the listener's expectations. The prefix 'do-' strongly intensifies 'shirouto,' positioning the speaker as a complete amateur or someone who really does not know much. Because 'nande, ...' gives the reason first, it is likely to be followed by expressions such as 'I might not be much help,' 'I may say something strange,' or 'please teach me.' This is not merely self-introduction. It is a prefacing expression that hands the speaker's limitation to the listener before speaking or participating.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting one's limitation

adjusting expectations

expression of humility

preface before speaking or participating

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

humble expression

expectation adjustment

limitation of ability

prefacing expression

It'll take a little longer.

もうちょっと掛^かかる。

Mou chotto kakaru.

It'll take a little longer.

Variants

- もう少し^{すこ}掛^かかる。

It'll take a little longer.

- あと少し^{すこ}掛^かかる。

It will take a little more time.

- もうちょっと^{じかん}時間^{ひつよう}が必要だ。

It needs a bit more time.

Adjusted Expression

もう少^{しょうしょう}々^{じかん}、時間^かが掛かります。

It will take a little more time.

Example

A 「仕事^{しごと}、終^おわった？」 B 「もうちょっと掛^かかる」

A: Is the work finished? B: It'll take a little longer.

Notes

'Mou chotto kakaru' tells the listener that the task is not finished yet, while avoiding making the remaining time sound too large. 'Mou chotto' indicates that more time is still needed, but also suggests that the end is

not far away. 'Kakaru' means that time will be required. In the example, the listener asks whether the work is finished, and the speaker immediately adjusts that expectation: it is not done yet, but it should be done after a little more time.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

estimation of time reporting progress adjusting expectations holding off completion

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken time estimation progress report expectation adjustment
completion pending

What on earth

いったい^{ぜんたい}全体

Ittai zentai

What on earth

Variants

- いったい、いつ？
When on earth?
- いったい、^{だれ}誰が？
Who on earth?
- いったい、なんで？
Why on earth?

Adjusted Expression

どういふわけで、このようなことになったのでしょうか。

How did this happen?

Example

A 「^{かれ}彼、^い行っちゃったよ」 B 「いったい^{ぜんたい}全体、^{なに}何が^お起こったの？」

A: He left. B: What on earth happened?

Notes

'Ittai zentai' is used when an event or situation is hard to understand and the speaker asks a question with strong surprise or confusion. 'Ittai' alone already intensifies a question, but adding 'zentai' expands the force

of the question and gives the sense that the whole situation is puzzling: what is going on here? In the example, after hearing that he has left, the speaker has not yet organized the situation and first reacts with a strongly marked question: what on earth happened?

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasis of a question

expression of surprise

expression of confusion

demand for understanding the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

question emphasis

expression of surprise

expression of confusion

emphatic expression

What do you mean by that?

それ、どういうことですか？

Sore, dou iu koto desu ka?

What do you mean by that?

Variants

- それ、どういう意味ですか？
What do you mean by that?
- それ、どういう風に？
What does that mean?
- それ、どういうこと？
What do you mean?
- どういう意味？
How do you mean?

Adjusted Expression

それは、どういう意味でしょうか？

What does that mean?

Example

A 「今日は、無料です」 B 「それ、どういうことですか？」

A: Today is free of charge. B: What do you mean by that?

Notes

'Sore, dou iu koto desu ka?' is used when the speaker receives the listener's statement but cannot immediately understand its meaning or implication. 'Sore,' picks up the listener's previous utterance, and 'dou iu koto desu ka?' asks what that utterance means, or what reason or condition lies behind it. The expression does not merely ask for the meaning of a word. It returns the speaker's halt in understanding to the listener and asks for an explanation. In the example, 'Today is free of charge' is unexpected, so the speaker asks what the reason or arrangement is.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation of meaning

request for explanation

showing that understanding has stopped

checking the listener's statement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

meaning confirmation

request for explanation

halt in understanding

response to the listener's statement

This one, ...

こればかりは、 ...

Kore bakari wa, ...

This one, ...

Variants

- これだけは、 ...

This one, ...

- こればかりは、 ...

This is the one thing I can't, ...

- これはちょっと、 ...

This is a bit, ...

-

There's nothing I can do about this one.

Adjusted Expression

これかんに関しては、私わたしにはどうすることもできません。

There is nothing I can do about this.

Example

A 「この問題もんだい、解決かいけつできる？」 B 「ごめんね、こればかりは、どうすることも...」

A: Can you solve this problem? B: Sorry, there's nothing I can do about this one.

Notes

'Kore bakari wa, ...' marks the matter as an exception and shows that the speaker cannot do anything about this particular case. 'Kore bakari wa' draws a line: other things may be possible, but this one is different. When it is followed by an unfinished phrase such as 'dou suru koto mo ...,' the impossibility or refusal is understood even without being fully stated. Together with a troubled expression or hesitation, it becomes an incomplete sentence that shows the speaker's limit while still leaving consideration for the listener.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

marking something as an exception

presenting impossibility

communicating one's limit

soft refusal to the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

exception marking

expression of impossibility

presentation of limitation

incomplete sentence

... is necessary.

ひつよう
...は必要。

... wa hitsuyou.

... is necessary.

Variants

- ...が^{ひつよう}必要。
... is necessary.
- ...は^{ひつす}必須。
... is essential.
- ...が^{ひつす}必須。
... is required.

Adjusted Expression

ひつよう
...は必要です。

... is necessary.

Example

A 「この書類^{しよるい}、提出^{ていしゅつ}しなきゃ？」 B 「うん、これは必要^{ひつよう}」

A: Do I have to submit this document? B: Yes, this one is necessary.

Notes

'... wa hitsuyou' is used to give an immediate judgment about whether something is necessary. The speaker can say 'hitsuyou desu,' but in conversation, stopping at 'hitsuyou' presents the judgment briefly. 'Kore

wa hitsuyou' does not merely mean that the document is important. In response to the question of whether it must be submitted, it returns the judgment that this document cannot be omitted and is required as a condition. A key point is that 'hitsuyou,' which looks like a noun or adjectival-noun stem, functions directly as the predicate.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of necessity presentation of a condition immediate presentation of judgment
response with an omitted copula

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of necessity condition presentation
nominal predicate copula omission

Speaking of...

...といえは、 ...

... to ieba, ...

Speaking of...

Variants

- ...といえは、 ...

Speaking of...

- ...ってといえは、 ...

Now that you mention...

- ...といえは、 ...ね。

Speaking of..., right?

Adjusted Expression

かんれん 関連する わだい 話題として、 ... い について といえは、 ...

As a related topic, speaking of ...

Example

A 「きのう 昨日、えいが 映画を み 見たよ」 B 「へえ、えいが 映画といえは、さいきん 最近、かんとく あの監督の しんさく 新作が
こうかい 公開されたね」

A: I watched a movie yesterday. B: Oh, speaking of movies, that director's new film was released recently.

Notes

'... to ieba, ...' picks up a word or topic from the listener's previous utterance and uses it as a starting point for a related topic. It does not

completely change the subject. Rather, it keeps a connection with the previous topic while inserting the speaker's association or related information. In 'eiga to ieba,' the speaker takes the word 'movie' from the listener's statement and uses it to move the conversation toward another piece of information: the director's new film.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

connecting topics

moving to a related topic

presenting an association

developing the conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

topic connection

shift to a related topic

activation of association

conversation development

Strangely, ...

みょう
妙に、 ...

Myou ni, ...

Strangely, ...

Variants

- 不思議ふしぎに、 ...

Strangely, ...

- 変へんに、 ...

Oddly, ...

- 奇妙きみょうに、 ...

In a strange way, ...

Adjusted Expression

みょう かん
妙みょうに感じかんられるのですが、 ...

It feels strange, but ...

Example

A 「最近さいきん、疲れつかやすいなあ」 B 「うん、妙みょうに体からだが重おもいし、眠ねむれないこともあるよね」

A: I've been getting tired easily lately. B: Yeah, my body feels strangely heavy, and sometimes I can't sleep.

Notes

'Myou ni, ...' shows that something feels different from usual before the speaker can clearly explain why. 'Myou' does not simply label something as strange. It creates the sense that something is not normal, or that something is hard to explain but noticeable. In 'myou ni karada ga omoi,' the speaker shares a bodily sensation that feels different from usual before naming a clear cause or condition.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of unease

presenting a difference from the usual

emphasis of sensation

self-observation before the reason is clear

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of unease

expression of sensation

reason not yet formed

self-observation

To put it very roughly, ...

すごく、^{ざつ}雑に^い言うけど、...

Sugoku, zatsu ni iu kedo, ...

To put it very roughly, ...

Variants

- ^{おお}大まかに^い言うと、...

To put it very roughly, ...

- ^{ざつ}ざっくり^い言うと、...

Roughly speaking, ...

- ^{かんたん}簡単に^い言うと、...

To put it simply, ...

-

Broadly speaking, ...

Adjusted Expression

^{おお}大まかに^い言うと、...

Broadly speaking, ...

Example

A 「この計画、^{けいかく}詳しく^{くわ}説明して」 B 「まずね、^{ざつ}すごく^い雑に^い言うけど、^{よう}要は^{りえき}利益
を^{さいだいか}最大化^{もくてき}することが目的だよ」

A: Please explain this plan in detail. B: First, to put it very roughly, the main point is to maximize profits.

Notes

'Sugoku, zatsu ni iu kedo, ...' is used when the speaker puts forward an understanding or judgment that has not yet been fully organized. 'Zatsu ni' does not only admit that the explanation is rough. It also tells the listener that what follows is a provisional outline before the details have been adjusted. In immediate conversation, speakers do not always begin after fully organizing what they want to say. This expression opens a space for saying: this may need later correction, but roughly, this is the direction of my thought.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a rough outline

temporarily setting precision aside

simplifying information

opening an explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

rough outline

information simplification

prefacing expression

suspension of precision

In the end, maybe it is...

けっきょく
結局、...じゃないかって。

Kekkyoku, ... ja nai ka tte.

In the end, maybe it is...

Variants

- さいしゅうてき
最終的に、...じゃないかって。

In the end, maybe it is...

- けっきょく
結局のところ、...じゃないかって。

Ultimately, maybe it is...

- よう
要するに、...じゃないかって。

In short, maybe it comes down to...

Adjusted Expression

けっきょく
結局、...ではないかと思います。

In the end, I think it may be ...

Example

A 「この^{もんだい}問題、^{かいけつ}解決できる？」 B 「うーん、^{けっきょく}結局、^{じかん}時間が^か掛かるし、^{ひよう}費用も^{たか}高いから、^{むずか}難しいんじゃないかって」

A: Can we solve this problem? B: Hmm, in the end, maybe it's difficult because it takes time and costs a lot.

Notes

'Kekkyoku, ... ja nai ka tte' is used when the speaker has considered several conditions or circumstances and offers a provisional conclusion to the listener. 'Kekkyoku' gathers the preceding details and points to where the matter finally seems to land. '... ja nai ka' is not a direct assertion. It presents a judgment as something that seems reasonable. The final 'tte' keeps the judgment from being fully closed and leaves room for the listener to consider it as well. In the example, after considering time and cost, the speaker does not directly assert that the problem is difficult, but offers that conclusion as a shareable view.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a provisional conclusion

presenting a summary

sharing a judgment

avoiding direct assertion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

conclusion presentation

summary expression

unfinished expression

avoidance of direct assertion

Could you...?

...てくれない？

... te kurenai?

Could you...?

Variants

- ...てくれませんか？
Could you...?
- ...てもらえますか？
Would you...?
- ...ていただけますか？
Could I ask you to...?

Adjusted Expression

...ていただけますか？

Could I ask you to...?

Example

A 「^{てっだ}手伝ってくれない？」 B 「うん、いいよ」

A: Could you help me? B: Sure, no problem.

Notes

'... te kurenai?' is a casual request expression used when the speaker wants the listener to do something for them. Although it has the form of a negative question, it is not used here to state a negative meaning. It asks whether the listener will do the action for the speaker. 'Kureru'

marks the listener's action as something beneficial to the speaker. By using a question rather than a command, the speaker leaves room for the listener to refuse while still asking for cooperation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of request appeal to the listener request for cooperation

leaving room for acceptance

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken request expression request for cooperation

negative question giving-receiving expression

Wasn't there...?

...ありませんでしたっけ？

... arimasen deshita kke?

Wasn't there...?

Variants

- ...なかったっけ？
Wasn't there...?
- ...じゃなかったっけ？
Wasn't it...?
- ...ではなかったっけ？
Wasn't that...?

Adjusted Expression

...はありましたでしたか？

Wasn't there...?

Example

A 「^{きのう}昨日、^{ひと}あの人、^あ会ったよね」 B 「^{なまえ}うん、^{おも}名前は^だ思い出せないけど、^{たし}確か、
^{あたら}新しい^{ぶちょう}部長じゃなかったっけ？」

A: We met that person yesterday, right? B: Yeah, I can't remember his name, but wasn't he the new department manager?

Notes

'... arimasen deshita kke?' is used when the speaker checks a past event or piece of information against the listener's memory. 'Arimasen deshita

ka?' can ask whether something existed or happened in the past, but adding 'kke' gives the utterance the sense of memory checking: I think this was the case, but I want to confirm it. The speaker is not asking about something completely unknown. Rather, they offer a partially recalled piece of information and try to align it with the listener's memory. In the example, 'janakatta kke?' presents the idea that he was the new department manager not as a firm assertion, but as something to be confirmed from memory.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation of memory checking past information reconfirmation with the listener
presenting partially recalled information

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken memory confirmation reconfirmation expression
checking past information kke

That's not it.

それ、^{ちが}違うよ。

Sore, chigau yo.

That's not it.

Variants

- それ、^{まちが}間違ってるよ。

That's not it.

- それ、^{ちが}違いますよ。

That's wrong.

- それ、^{ごかい}誤解だよ。

That's incorrect.

-

That's a misunderstanding.

Adjusted Expression

それは、^{まちが}間違っています。

That is incorrect.

Example

A 「これは、^{わたし}私がもらったもの」 B 「ううん、それ、^{ちが}違うよ。みんながもらったものだよ」

A: This is mine. I got this. B: No, that's not it. Everyone got one.

Notes

'Sore, chigau yo' is used when the speaker responds to the listener's statement or understanding and immediately corrects it. 'Chigau' does not only judge something as wrong. It can also show a mismatch: that is not the object, not the interpretation, or not the direction. 'Sore,' picks up the listener's previous statement or understanding, and 'chigau yo' stops it from continuing as it is. The final 'yo' makes the correction something the speaker offers for the listener to notice. In the example, A thinks the item belongs only to them, and B corrects that understanding by saying that everyone received one.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

pointing out an error

correcting recognition

stopping the listener's statement

guiding the listener toward the correct understanding

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

error pointing

correction expression

correction of recognition

response to the listener's statement

Switch gears there.

そこは^き切り^か替えて。

Soko wa kirikaete.

Shift your mindset there.

Variants

- そこは^か変えて。
Shift your mindset there.
- そこは^き切り^か替えなさい。
Switch gears there.
- そこは^きも^きちを^か切り^か替えて。
Change your approach there.
- That is where you need to shift.

Adjusted Expression

そういうときは、^きも^{かんが}や^{かた}考え方を^き切り^か替えて^{たいおう}対応するとよいでしょう。

In such cases, it may be better to shift your mindset and respond differently.

Example

A 「^{しごと}仕事^{いそが}が忙しくて、^{つか}疲れたよ」 B 「そういうときは、そこは^き切り^か替えて、^{きぶん}気分^かを変えたほうがいいよ」

A: Work has been busy, and I'm tired. B: In that kind of situation, you need to switch gears and change your mood.

Notes

'Soko wa kirikaete' is used when the listener is caught in a certain feeling or situation, and the speaker suggests changing how that part is handled.

'Soko' does not refer to a physical place. It points to the specific point, phase, or emotional sticking point that the listener is dealing with.

'Kirikaete' asks the listener to shift their way of thinking, mood, or action into another mode. In the example, the listener is being pulled down by work and fatigue, and the speaker advises them not to stay in that state but to switch gears and change their mood.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

prompting a change of mindset

changing one's response strategy

giving advice to the listener

moving out of a stuck state

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

advice expression

change of mindset

change of response

directive expression

I have a feeling that's the case.

そんな^{かん}感じがする。

Sonna kanji ga suru.

I have a feeling that's the case.

Variants

- そんな^き気がする。

I have a feeling that's the case.

- なんとなくそんな^{かん}感じがする。

I feel that too.

- ^{みょう}妙にそんな^{かん}感じがする。

Somehow, I get that feeling.

-

I have a strange feeling about that.

Adjusted Expression

なんとなく、そんな^{かん}感じがします。

Somehow, I feel that may be the case.

Example

A 「彼女、来ないかなあ？」 B 「うん、そんな^{かん}感じがする。来たとしても、ずいぶん^{おく}遅れて来るんじゃない？」

A: I wonder if she might not come. B: Yeah, I have a feeling that's the case. Even if she comes, she may arrive quite late.

Notes

'Sonna kanji ga suru' is used when the speaker cannot give a clear reason, but wants to share the feeling that a situation is probably like that. 'Sonna' picks up the impression or possibility that has just been mentioned in the conversation, and 'kanji ga suru' presents it not as a firm assertion but as a felt judgment. For that reason, this expression is less like a strong prediction and more like a response meaning, yes, I think it is probably going in that direction too. In the example, A suggests that she may not come, and B responds with 'sonna kanji ga suru' to show that they share the same impression.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing intuitive agreement

sharing an impression

expression of intuition

presenting a sense or hunch

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

sharing a felt impression

expression of intuition

sharing a view

response expression

Oh, I ended up saying something kind of weird,

ああ、なんか、^{へん}変なこと、^い言っちゃって、
て、

aa, nanka, hen na koto, icchatte,

Oh, I ended up saying something kind of weird,

Variants

- ああ、なんか、おかしなこと、^い言っちゃって、
Oh, I ended up saying something kind of strange,
- ああ、なんか、^{へん}変なこと、^{はな}話しちゃって、
Oh, I ended up talking about something weird,
- ああ、なんか、^{へん}変なこと、^い言っちゃって、
Oh, I said something kind of weird,

Adjusted Expression

しょうしょう ふてきせつ はつげん もう わけ
少々、不適切な発言をしてしまい、申し訳ありませんでした。

I made a slightly inappropriate remark, and I apologize.

Example

A 「^{きのう}昨日、^あ会ったとき、^{へん}変なこと、^い言っちゃって、ごめんね」 B 「^きううん、気にしないで」

A: Sorry for saying something weird when we met yesterday. B: No, don't worry about it.

Notes

"Oh, I ended up saying something kind of weird," is used when the speaker looks back on what they said and offers it to the listener as something that may have sounded a little strange. "Nanka" shows that the evaluation is still vague, and "icchatte" presents the utterance as something the speaker ended up saying unintentionally. Because the sentence stops with "te," the apology is not fully completed, leaving room for the listener to respond with something like "Don't worry about it."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of awkwardness after speaking

sharing of self-assessment

entry into an apology

softening of conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

incomplete sentence

expression of apology

expression of self-assessment

expression of conversation softening

Just right.

ちょうど
丁度いい。

choudo ii.

Just right.

Variants

- ちょうど
丁度いいね。

Just right.

- ぴったりだね。

It's perfect.

- てきせつ
適切だね。

It's appropriate.

Adjusted Expression

ちょうど
丁度よいです。

It is just right.

Example

A 「この服、サイズ、ちょうどいいね」 B 「うん、似合ってるよ」

A: This fits just right. B: Yes, it suits you.

Notes

"Just right" is used when the speaker evaluates something as fitting a standard or expectation at that moment. It can mean not too big or too small, not too strong or too weak, not too much or too little. The focus is

not simply that something is good, but that it fits the present conditions without excess or deficiency.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of suitability

in-the-moment evaluation

sharing of satisfaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of evaluation

expression of suitability

expression of satisfaction sharing

I do things like taking walks, but...

さんぽ
散歩したりしてるんですけど、

sanpo shitari shiteru n desu kedo,

I do things like taking walks, but...

Variants

- さんぽ 散歩したり、か もの 買い物したりしてるんですけど、
I do things like taking walks and shopping, but...
- うんどう 運動したりしてるんですけど、
I do things like exercising, but...
- どくしょ 読書したりしてるんですけど、
I do things like reading, but...

Adjusted Expression

たとえば、さんぽ 散歩、どくしょ 読書、りょうり 料理など、さまざまなことをしています。

For example, I do various things such as taking walks, reading books, and cooking.

Example

A 「さいきん ひま 最近、暇なの？」 B 「うん、さんぽ 散歩したりしてるんですけど、なに しゅみ 何かいい趣味があればおし 教えてくれるとうれしいな」

A: Do you have a lot of free time lately? B: Yes, I do things like taking walks, but I'd be happy if you could suggest a good hobby.

Notes

"I do things like taking walks, but..." is used when the speaker explains what they have been doing recently by giving one example, while leaving a sense that it is not quite enough. "Shitari shiteru" suggests that taking walks is only one activity among others. Because the sentence stops with "kedo," the explanation is not completed there. It leaves room for the next move, such as asking for advice or implying that the current activities are not fully satisfying.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation of recent life presentation of what one is doing for now

introduction to a consultation implied insufficiency

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken incomplete sentence expression of recent-life explanation

expression of consultation introduction expression of exemplification

That's pretty amazing, isn't it?

すごいじゃないですか。

sugoi ja nai desu ka.

That's pretty amazing, isn't it?

Variants

- ^{すば}素晴らしいじゃないですか。

That's wonderful, isn't it?

- ^{おどろ}驚くべきことじゃないですか。

That's surprising, isn't it?

- ^{かんとうてき}感動的じゃないですか。

That's impressive, isn't it?

Adjusted Expression

それは、^{すば}素晴らしいですね。

That's wonderful.

Example

A 「^{あたら}新しい^{くるま}車、^か買ったんだ」 B 「へえ、^{くるま}すごいじゃないですか。どんな車？」

A: I bought a new car. B: Wow, that's pretty amazing. What kind of car is it?

Notes

"That's pretty amazing, isn't it?" is used when the speaker gives an immediate positive evaluation of the listener's action, achievement, or

situation. "Sugoi" expresses a strong positive evaluation, but "ja nai desu ka" makes it sound like something the listener can also recognize as true. It is therefore not just an expression of surprise, but a response that acknowledges the listener's achievement and keeps the conversation moving in a positive direction.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of praise

sharing of positive evaluation

response to the listener's achievement

drawing the listener into shared recognition

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of praise

expression of positive evaluation

expression of shared recognition

response expression

It's totally fine.

ぜんぜんいいですよ。

zenzen ii desu yo.

It's totally fine.

Variants

- まったく問題もんだいないですよ。
There's absolutely no problem.
- ぜんぜん大丈夫だいじょうぶですよ。
It's totally okay.
- ぜんぜん気きにしないでください。
Please don't worry about it at all.

Adjusted Expression

まったく問題もんだいありません。

There is absolutely no problem.

Example

A 「遅おくれてごめんね」 B 「ううん、ぜんぜんいいですよ」

A: Sorry for being late. B: No, it's totally fine.

Notes

"It's totally fine" is used in response to the listener's apology or hesitation, strongly indicating that there is no problem and reducing the listener's burden. "Zenzen" was traditionally associated with negative

expressions, but in spoken Japanese it can also combine with positive expressions such as "ii" or "daijoubu." Here, it does more than simply say that something is fine. It immediately cancels the listener's concern and reassures them that they do not need to worry.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of reassurance response to an apology conveyance that there is no problem
reduction of the listener's burden

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of reassurance response to an apology
expression of acceptance positive response expression

I'm totally fine.

ぜんぜん^{へいき}平気です。

zenzen heiki desu.

I'm totally fine.

Variants

- まったく^{もんだい}問題ないです。
There's absolutely no problem.
- ぜんぜん^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫です。
I'm totally okay.
- ぜんぜん^き気にしていません。
I don't mind at all.

Adjusted Expression

まったく^{もんだい}問題ありません。

There is absolutely no problem.

Example

A 「^{しんぱい}心配しないで、^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫？」 B 「うん、ぜんぜん^{へいき}平気です」

A: Don't worry. Are you okay? B: Yes, I'm totally fine.

Notes

"I'm totally fine" is used in response to the listener's concern, indicating that the speaker is not having any problem. "Heiki" suggests that the speaker is not affected by pain, anxiety, difficulty, or awkwardness. With

"zenzen," the response becomes stronger: the speaker is not just somewhat okay, but has no problem at all. While No.665 "zenzen ii desu yo" accepts the listener's action or apology, this expression presents the speaker's own state in order to reassure the listener.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation of one's own state response to concern conveyance that there is no problem

expression of reassuring the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of reassurance response to concern

expression of state explanation positive response expression

I'm totally fine.

ぜんぜん^{へいき}平気です。

zenzen heiki desu.

I'm totally fine.

Variants

- まったく^{もんだい}問題ないです。
There's absolutely no problem.
- ぜんぜん^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫です。
I'm totally okay.
- ぜんぜん^き気にしていません。
I don't mind at all.

Adjusted Expression

まったく^{もんだい}問題ありません。

There is absolutely no problem.

Example

A 「^{だいじょうぶ}大丈夫？ ^{いた}痛くない？」 B 「うん、ぜんぜん^{へいき}平気です」

A: Are you okay? Does it hurt? B: Yes, I'm totally fine.

Notes

"I'm totally fine" is used in response to the listener's concern, indicating that the speaker is not having any problem. "Heiki" suggests that the speaker is not affected by pain, anxiety, difficulty, or awkwardness. With

"zenzen," the response becomes stronger: the speaker is not just somewhat okay, but has no problem at all. While No.665 "zenzen ii desu yo" accepts the listener's action or apology, this expression presents the speaker's own state in order to reassure the listener.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explanation of one's own state response to concern conveyance that there is no problem

expression of reassuring the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of reassurance response to concern

expression of state explanation positive response expression

While using ...

...^{つか}を使いつつ、

... o tsukai tsutsu,

While using ...

Variants

- ...^{りよう}を利用しつつ、
While utilizing ...
- ...^{かつよう}を活用しつつ、
While making use of ...
- ...^{もち}を用いながら、
While employing ...

Adjusted Expression

...^{つか}を使いながら、^{さぎょう}作業をしています。

I am working while using ...

Example

A「^{あた}新しいソフト、^{つか}使ってみた？」 B「うん、^{きのう}機能^{つか}を使いつつ、^{そうさ}操作^なに慣れてるところ」

A: Have you tried the new software? B: Yes, I'm getting used to the controls while using its features.

Notes

"While using ..." indicates that the act of using something and another action or change are proceeding at the same time. "Tsukaitsutsu" is close to "tsukainagara," but it sounds slightly more explanatory and is often used when describing a working process or approach. Because the expression stops with "tsutsu," it does not complete the sentence by itself. It leads into the next action, such as getting used to something, adjusting it, or checking how it works.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of simultaneous progression

explanation of a working process

presentation of getting used to something while using it

introduction to the next explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

explanatory expression

expression of simultaneous progression

expression of working-process explanation

incomplete sentence

Before I knew it, I was

気づいたら、...してました。

kizuitara ... shitemashita.

Before I knew it, I was

Variants

- 気がついたら、...してました。
Before I realized it, I was
- いつの間にか、...してました。
Somehow, I found myself
- 気づいたときには、...していました。
By the time I noticed, I was

Adjusted Expression

気づいたときには、仕事を終わっていました。

By the time I realized it, I had finished my work.

Example

A 「昨日、寝るつもりだったのに、気づいたら、朝まで映画を見てしまったよ」 B 「それは大変だね」

A: I meant to go to bed yesterday, but before I knew it, I had ended up watching movies until morning. B: That's rough.

Notes

"Kizuitara, ... shitemashita" is used when the speaker looks back and realizes that they had drifted into an action or state without fully noticing the process at the time. "Kizuitara" does not simply mean the literal moment of noticing. Rather, it indicates retrospective recognition: only at that point does the speaker become aware of what had been going on. "... shitemashita" is a colloquial form of "... shite imashita," and it gives the utterance a tone of looking back with a bit of surprise.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of retrospective noticing

sharing of an unintentional flow of action

expression of the passage of time

explanation of an event

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of retrospective noticing

expression of unconscious action

expression of time passage

expression of event explanation

There are things like ...

...とかあるんですよ。

... toka aru n desu yo.

There are things like ...

Variants

- ...とかもあるんですよ。
There are also things like ...
- ...みたいなものもあるんですよ。
There are things kind of like ... too.
- ...なんかもあるんですよ。
You can even find things like ...

Adjusted Expression

...などもあります。

There are also things such as ...

Example

A 「最近、面白い本、読んだ？」 B 「うん、今まであまり見かけなかったジャンルとかあるんですよ」

A: Have you read any interesting books lately? B: Yes, there are genres I hadn't really seen before.

Notes

"There are things like ..." is used when the speaker brings an example or type into the conversation and lets the listener know that such things

exist. "Toka" presents the item loosely as one example, while "aru n desu yo" presents it as something the speaker has found, knows about, or thinks the listener may not yet know. It is not merely a statement of existence. It shares information while drawing the listener's attention.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of exemplification presentation of information sharing of discovery

appeal to what the listener may not know

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of exemplification

expression of information presentation expression of discovery sharing

conversation-introducing expression

It's an incredible app.

とんでもないアプリですよ。

tondemo nai apuri desu yo.

It's an incredible app.

Variants

- すごいアプリですよ。

It's an amazing app.

- 驚くべきアプリですよ。

It's a surprising app.

- 画期的なアプリですよ。

It's a groundbreaking app.

Adjusted Expression

それは、非常に優れたアプリですね。

That is an excellent app.

Example

A 「この新しいアプリ、使ってみた？」 B 「うん、とんでもないアプリですよ。すごく便利で役に立つ」

A: Have you tried this new app? B: Yes, it's an incredible app. It's really convenient and useful.

Notes

"It's an incredible app" indicates that the app made such a strong impression that an ordinary evaluative word is not enough. "Tondemonai" can be negative or positive depending on the context, but here it gives a positive evaluation: the app is far beyond what the speaker expected. With "desu yo," the speaker presents this surprise and evaluation to the listener, suggesting that the listener should also recognize its value.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of strong evaluation

sharing of surprise

presentation of positive evaluation

recommendation to the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of strong evaluation

expression of shared surprise

expression of positive evaluation

recommendation expression

Overflowing with love.

^{あい}
...愛があふれる。

... ai ga afureru.

Overflowing with love.

Variants

- ...^{あいじょう}愛情があふれる。
Overflowing with affection.
- ...^{おも}思いやりがあふれる。
Overflowing with compassion.
- ...^{やさ}優しさがあふれる。
Overflowing with kindness.

Adjusted Expression

...には、^{ふか} ^{あいじょう}深い愛情があります。

There is deep affection in it.

Example

A 「この映画、^{えいが}感動的^{かんだうてき}だったね」 B 「うん、^{あい}愛があふれる^すストーリー^{りー}で、^{こころ}心に
^{ひび}響いたよ」

A: That movie was really moving, wasn't it? B: Yes, it was a story full of love, and it really stayed with me.

Notes

"... ai ga afureru" is an evaluative expression used when the speaker feels that warm emotions such as love or compassion are so full in a work, a person, or a scene that they seem to flow outward. "Afureru" suggests not just the existence of emotion, but a sense that it cannot be contained and is visibly overflowing. For that reason, the expression works less as an objective description and more as a way for the speaker to share an immediate impression of warmth with the listener.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

evaluation of emotional richness

sharing of warmth

positive evaluation of a work or a person's character

expression of impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of emotional evaluation

expression of warmth

expression of positive evaluation

expression of impression

It's not something to ask about.

き
聞くようなことじゃないし。

kiku you na koto ja nai shi.

It's not something to ask about.

Variants

- たず 尋ねるようなことじゃないし。

It's not something to inquire about.

- はな 話すようなことじゃないし。

It's not something to talk about.

- ふ 触れるようなことじゃないし。

It's not something to touch on.

Adjusted Expression

き
聞くべきことではありません。

It is not something that should be asked about.

Example

A 「^{かのじょ}彼女、^{こども}子供いるの？」 B 「^し知らない。き聞くようなことじゃないし、ちよつと^{ぷらいべーと}プライベートなことだし」

A: Does she have children? B: I don't know. It's not something to ask about, and it's a bit private.

Notes

"It's not something to ask about" is used when the speaker judges that asking about a certain topic is not appropriate and draws a boundary in the conversation. "Kiku you na koto ja nai" does not simply mean that the information is unnecessary. It indicates that, considering the relationship, the private nature of the topic, or the situation, one should not step that far into it. The final "shi" gives one reason while leaving room for other reasons as well, helping redirect the conversation away from the topic.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

setting a boundary around a topic

consideration for privacy

restraint from asking

redirecting the conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

incomplete sentence

expression of topic restriction

expression of privacy consideration

expression of conversation redirection

What is this?

なん
何だこれ？

nanda kore?

What is this?

Variants

- これは何？

What is this?

- これって何？

What is this thing?

- これ、何？

What is this supposed to be?

Adjusted Expression

これは何ですか。

What is this?

Example

A 「新しいガジェットを買ったよ」 B 「何だこれ？ どうやって使うの？」

A: I bought a new gadget. B: What is this? How do you use it?

Notes

"What is this?" in this entry is an immediate reaction to something unexpected or hard to understand. It is not a calm request for information like "What is this?" in a neutral setting. The expression first

conveys surprise or strangeness, as if the speaker is saying that the object or situation does not fit ordinary expectations. It is used when the speaker sees something strange, unfamiliar, or different from what they expected.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of surprise expression of discomfort or strangeness

reaction to something hard to classify request for explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of surprise expression of strangeness

expression of requesting explanation immediate response expression

It almost happened.

...ところでしたよ。

... tokoro deshita yo.

It almost happened.

Variants

- ^{あぶ}危ないところでしたよ。

That was a close call.

- もう少し^{すこ}で...ところでしたよ。

It almost ...

- ^{かんいっぽつ}間一髪でしたよ。

It was a narrow escape.

Adjusted Expression

もう少し^{すこ}で、その出来事^{できごと}が起^おこるところでした。

That event almost happened.

Example

A 「車^{くるま}に轢^ひかれそうになったんだ」 B 「ええ、^{あぶ}危ないところでしたよ」

A: I almost got hit by a car. B: Wow, that was a close call.

Notes

"... tokoro deshita yo" indicates that an event came close to happening but did not actually happen. It is used with a preceding verb phrase, as in "I almost got hit" or "I almost dropped it." The expression looks back on

the situation after the danger or failure has already been avoided, carrying a sense of "that was close." The final "yo" presents that sense of danger or relief to the listener.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of something that almost happened

sharing of danger

conveyance of tension

expression of relief

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of danger

expression of an unrealized event

expression of tension

expression of relief

I don't need that kind of thing.

そんなもん、いらないよ。

sonna mon, iranai yo.

I don't need that kind of thing.

Variants

- そんなもの、いらないよ。
I don't need that kind of thing.
- そんなの、いらないよ。
I don't need that.
- そんなものは、^{ひつよう}必要ないよ。
That kind of thing isn't necessary.

Adjusted Expression

そのようなものは、^{ひつよう}必要ありません。

I do not need that kind of thing.

Example

A 「^{あたら}新しい^がガ^じジ^えェ^っト^とを買ったよ」 B 「そんなもん、いらないよ。いまのまま^{じゅうぶん}で十分だよ」

A: I bought a new gadget. B: I don't need that kind of thing. What I have now is enough.

Notes

"I don't need that kind of thing" is used when the speaker strongly pushes back against something the listener has brought up, treating it as

unnecessary for them. "Sonna mon" is a casual form of "sonna mono," but it does more than refer to the object. It also makes the object sound low in value. For that reason, "iranai yo" is not only a denial of necessity, but also a refusal: the speaker is saying that it is not worth accepting. Since it directly rejects the listener's suggestion, gift, or idea, it can sound harsh depending on the situation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

denial of necessity downgrading of value expression of refusal

resistance to the listener's suggestion

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of refusal expression of denial of necessity

expression of downgrading value expression of resistance

Calm down.

お
落ちついて。

ochitsuite.

Calm down.

Variants

- お落ちついてください。
Please calm down.
- まあ、お落ちついて。
Just calm down for a moment.
- いちど、お落ちつこう。
Let's calm down first.

Adjusted Expression

お
落ちついてください。

Please calm down.

Example

A 「どうしよう、さいふがない！」 B 「お落ちついて。だいじょうぶだから、まずかばんを見てみよう」

A: What should I do? My wallet is gone! B: Calm down. It's okay. Let's check your bag first.

Notes

"Calm down" is used when the listener is panicking, rushing, or emotionally upset, and the speaker wants them to stop reacting for a moment and regain composure. It is not only reassurance, but also an entry point for checking the situation or deciding what to do next. However, because it treats the listener as someone who is not calm at that moment, it can sound commanding or condescending depending on the tone and relationship. Expressions such as "Just calm down for a moment" or "Let's calm down first" can make it softer.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouragement to calm down

expression of reassurance

introduction to sorting out the situation

restraint of the listener's reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of reassurance

expression of emotional regulation

expression of response restraint

address expression

And then, before I knew it, ...

で、^き気がついたら、...

de, ki ga tsuitara, ...

And then, before I knew it, ...

Variants

- で、^き気づいたときには、...
And then, by the time I realized it, ...
- で、^き気づかないうちに、...
And then, without noticing, ...
- で、^き気づけば、...
And then, before I knew it, ...

Adjusted Expression

それで、^き気がついたときには、もう^{すうじつ}数日^たが経っていました。

So, by the time I realized it, several days had already passed.

Example

A 「で、^き気がついたら、^{あさ}朝^{えいが}まで映画^みを見てしまってた」 B 「で、そのまま^ね寝ないで来たの？」

A: And then, before I knew it, I had ended up watching movies until morning. B: So you came without sleeping?

Notes

"And then, before I knew it, ..." takes up the previous flow of the story and introduces a resulting state that the speaker only noticed afterward. "De," is not just a neutral connector. It lets the story slide from the previous event into the next result. "Ki ga tsuitara" suggests that the speaker was not fully aware of the process while it was happening, and then retells the event from the point where they noticed the result.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

connection in the flow of narration

expression of retrospective noticing

expression of the passage of time

introduction to a resulting state

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

chain-connecting expression

expression of retrospective noticing

expression of time passage

expression of event explanation

What is ...?

...って、^{なに}何？

... tte, nani?

What is ...?

Variants

- ...って、^{なん}何のこと？
What does ... mean?
- ...って、^{いみ}どういう意味？
What do you mean by ...?
- ...って、^{なに}^さ何を指してるの？
What is ... referring to?

Adjusted Expression

...とは、^{なん}何のことですか。

What does ... mean?

Example

A 「^{こんど}今度のアップデートでAI^{ほじょ}補助が^{はい}入るらしいよ」 B 「AI^{ほじょ}補助って、^{なに}何？」

A: I heard the next update will include AI assistance. B: What is AI assistance?

Notes

"What is ...?" is used when the speaker picks up a word or expression just used by the listener and asks what it means or what it refers to. "Tte" lifts

the previous word into the focus of the conversation, and "nani?" requests an explanation. It is not only a question about an unknown word. It also pauses the flow of the conversation and hands the expression back to the listener, asking how it should be understood.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of checking meaning

request for explanation

picking up the listener's word

temporary pause in the conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of checking meaning

expression of requesting explanation

echo-question expression

conversation-adjusting expression

If there is someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation, ...

そんな^{かいわ}会話が^{ひと}できる人が、^{ちか}近くにいる
と、 ...

sonna kaiwa ga dekiru hito ga, chikaku ni iru to, ...

If there is someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation, ...

Variants

- そんな^{かいわ}会話が^{ひと}できる人が、^{ちか}近くにいるといいな。

It would be nice to have someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation.

- そんな^{かいわ}会話が^{ひと}できる人が、^{ちか}近くにいると^{たす}助かるな。

It would be helpful to have someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation.

- そんな^{かいわ}会話が^{ひと}できる人が、^{ちか}近くにいると^{うれ}嬉しいな。

I would be happy to have someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation.

Adjusted Expression

そのような^{かいわ}会話が^{ひと}できる人が、^{ちか}近くにいるとよいですね。

It would be good to have someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation.

Example

A 「こういう話^{はなし}って、なかなかできる相手^{あいて}がないよね」 B 「うん。そんな
会^{かい}話^わができる人^{ひと}が、近^{ちか}くにいるといいんだけどね」

A: It's hard to find someone you can talk with about this kind of thing, isn't it? B: Yes. It would be nice to have someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation.

Notes

"If there is someone nearby who can have that kind of conversation, ..." expresses a desire or ideal: having someone nearby with whom that kind of conversation is possible. "Sonna kaiwa" refers back to the topic or atmosphere just mentioned, and it does not mean just any casual chat. It points to a conversation whose content, depth, or emotional tone can be shared. When the expression stops at "chikaku ni iru to," it leaves room for an evaluation such as "it would be nice," "it would help," or "I would be happy," indirectly showing the speaker's sense of isolation or hope.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

desire for someone to talk with

expression of an ideal relationship

sharing of the level of conversation desired

indirect expression of isolation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of desire

expression of sharing an ideal

expression of a conversation partner

expression of relationship

..., right?

...ますよね。

... *masu yo ne.*

..., right?

Variants

- ...ですよ。
..., right?
- ...しますよね。
That's how it is, right?
- ...なりますよね。
That happens, doesn't it?

Adjusted Expression

そういうことになりますね。

That is how it turns out, isn't it?

Example

A 「^{ふつう}普通、^{かんたん}こういうときは簡単に^{どうい}同意しますよね」 B 「しますよね」

A: Normally, in situations like this, people agree fairly easily, right? B: They do, don't they?

Notes

"... masu yo ne" is a sentence-final pattern in which the polite form "masu" is followed by "yo ne," asking the listener to share the speaker's recognition. "Yo" presents the speaker's judgment to the listener, and "ne"

seeks shared recognition. It is therefore not just agreement. It works to establish something as common ground in the conversation. The listener can also echo the previous predicate briefly, as in "shimasu yo ne" or "arimasu yo ne."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

sharing of confirmation

seeking agreement

drawing the listener into shared recognition

prompting the listener's response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

confirmation expression

expression of seeking agreement

expression of shared recognition

sentence-final expression

That's not what I'm saying.

そういうことを言^いってるんじゃないなくて、

...

sou iu koto o itteru n ja nakute, ...

That's not what I'm saying.

Variants

- そういうことを言^いってるんじゃないなくて、実^{じつ}は...
That's not what I'm saying. Actually, ...
- そういうことを言^いってるんじゃないなくて、つまり...
That's not what I'm saying. What I mean is ...
- そういうことを言^いってるんじゃないなくて、要^{よう}するに...
That's not what I'm saying. To put it simply, ...

Adjusted Expression

そういうことを言^いっているわけではなく、...

That is not what I mean.

Example

A 「つまり、この仕事^{しごと}、やりたくないんですね」 B 「いやいや、そういうことを言^いってるんじゃないなくて、この仕事^{しごと}には問題^{もんだい}があるってことです」

A: So, you don't want to do this job, right? B: No, no. That's not what I'm saying. What I mean is that there are problems with this job.

Notes

"That's not what I'm saying" is used when the listener has interpreted the speaker's words in a different direction, and the speaker wants to stop that interpretation. "Sou iu koto" refers to what the listener has just summarized or understood. "Itteru n ja nakute" denies that interpretation, saying that this was not the intended meaning. The speaker then restates what they actually wanted to say. The expression is not just a denial. It redirects the flow of the conversation and rebuilds the explanation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

correction of misunderstanding

stopping the listener's interpretation

restating one's intention

rebuilding the explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of correcting misunderstanding

expression of revising interpretation

expression of rebuilding an explanation

conversation-adjusting expression

Perhaps, ...

もしかしたら、...

moshikashitara, ...

Perhaps, ...

Variants

- もしかすると、...
Perhaps, ...
- もしかして、...
Maybe, ...
- ひょっとしたら、...
It is possible that ...

Adjusted Expression

その可能性かのうせいもあります。

That possibility also exists.

Example

A 「もしかしたら、今日きょう、雨あめが降ふるかもしれないね」 B 「うん、傘かさを持もっていったほうがいいかもね」

A: It might rain today. B: Yes, maybe we should take an umbrella.

Notes

"Perhaps, ..." is used to bring something into the conversation as a possibility, without treating it as certain. By presenting it as something that could be the case, the speaker can move on to judgments such as "it

might be," "it is possible," or "that may be true." "Moshikashite" often sounds more immediate and is often used when checking something with the listener or presenting a possibility just noticed. "Moshikashitara" sounds slightly more settled as a way of introducing a possibility.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presentation of possibility

sharing of speculation

expression of uncertainty

introduction to the next judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of possibility

expression of speculation

expression of uncertainty

conversation-introducing expression

That alone would have been enough.

それだけでいいのに...

sore dake de ii no ni...

That alone would have been enough.

Variants

- それだけで^{じゅうぶん}十分なのに。
That alone would have been enough.
- それだけで^{まんぞく}満足なのに。
That alone would have satisfied me.
- それだけでよかったのに。
That alone would have been fine.

Adjusted Expression

それだけで^{じゅうぶん}十分でした。

That alone would have been sufficient.

Example

A 「これに^{あた}ら^きの^う ^つい^か機能を追加しておいたよ」 B 「え、それだけでいいのに。あんまり^{ふく} ^ざつ複雑にしないでよ」

A: I added a new feature to this. B: Oh, that alone would have been enough. Don't make it too complicated.

Notes

"That alone would have been enough" is used when the speaker feels that one element or condition was already sufficient, but something more has

been added. "Sore dake de ii" expresses sufficiency, while "no ni" adds a sense of regret or dissatisfaction that the actual situation has moved away from that sufficient state. It can be used in response to the listener's kindness, addition, or extra effort, suggesting that it was appreciated but not necessary, or even excessive.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of sufficiency

reaction to excess

expression of regret

presentation of a mismatch with expectation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of sufficiency

expression of excess

expression of regret

expression of mismatch with expectation

Well, I think it's fine.

まあ、いいんじゃないですか。

maa, ii n ja nai desu ka.

Well, I think it's fine.

Variants

- まあ、いいんじゃない？
Well, I think it's fine.
- まあ、いいんじゃないでしょうか。
Well, it seems okay.
- まあ、いいんじゃないかな。
Well, that should be fine.

Adjusted Expression

とりあえずは、それでよいのではないかと^{おも}思います。

For now, I think that would be acceptable.

Example

A 「この^{あ い で あ}アイデア、どう^{おも}思う？」 B 「まあ、いいんじゃないですか。まずはそ^{ため}れで試してみましよう」

A: What do you think about this idea? B: Well, I think it's fine. Let's try it that way first.

Notes

"Well, I think it's fine" is used when the speaker responds to the listener's idea or proposal with a reserved positive evaluation. It does not express

strong approval. Rather, it suggests that there does not seem to be a major problem and that the idea is acceptable for now. "Maa" creates some distance from full approval, and "ii n ja nai desu ka" avoids making a direct assertion. The expression therefore works as modest approval or tentative acceptance, rather than enthusiastic praise.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

modest affirmation

presentation of acceptability

somewhat reserved evaluation

response to the listener's proposal

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of modest affirmation

evaluation expression

expression of acceptance

expression of reserved judgment

When you put it that way, ...

そういうふう^いに言^いわれると、...

sou iu fuu ni iwareru to, ...

When you put it that way, ...

Variants

- そういうふう^いに言^いわれると、確^{たし}かにそうですね。
When you put it that way, that's certainly true.
- そういうふう^いに言^いわれると、考^{かんが}えさせられますね。
When you put it that way, it makes me think.
- そういうふう^いに言^いわれると、納^な得^{とく}できますね。
When you put it that way, I can see your point.

Adjusted Expression

そのように説^{せつめい}明^{めい}されると、確^{たし}かにそうだと思^{おも}います。

When it is explained that way, I think that is certainly true.

Example

A 「この問^{もん}題^{だい}、複^{ふく}雑^{ざつ}に見^みえるけど、ここ^こに線^{せん}を引^ひけば、簡^{かん}単^{たん}だよな」 B 「そ^そう
い^いうふう^{ふう}に言^いわれると、確^{たし}かにそうですね」

A: This problem looks complicated, but if you draw a line here, it's simple, right? B: When you put it that way, that's certainly true.

Notes

"When you put it that way, ..." is used when the speaker's view has shifted somewhat after hearing the listener's explanation or framing. "Sou iu fuu ni" refers to the way the listener has put, understood, or explained the matter. With "iwareru to," the speaker responds that, if seen within that framing, it may indeed be true. It is not necessarily strong agreement. It shows the speaker accepting the listener's viewpoint and adjusting their own understanding or judgment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

acceptance of the listener's framing

expression of understanding

revision of one's view

movement toward agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of understanding

expression of accepting a viewpoint

expression of revising one's view

conversation-adjusting expression

No one see such a thing...

...なんてみんな^み見ていませんから、...

...nannte minna mite imasen kara, ...

No one see such a thing...

Variants

- ...なんてみんな見ていませんから、気にしないでください。
No one see such a thing, so please don't worry about it.
- ...なんてみんな見ていませんから、心配しないでください。
No one see such a thing, so please don't be concerned about it.
- ...なんてみんな見ていませんから、気にすることはありません。
No one see such a thing, so there's no need to worry about it.

Adjusted Expression

...なんてみんな見ていませんから、気にしないでください。

No one see such a thing, so please don't worry about it.

Example

A 「このミス、大勢^{おおぜい}の人に見^みられたんだ」 B 「いえいえ、他人^{ひと}のミス^{ミス}なんてみんな^み見ていませんから、気^きにしないでください」

A: This mistake was seen by a lot of people. B: No, no one care about someone's mistakes, so never mind.

Notes

'...nannte minna mite imasen kara, ...' is a colloquial expression used when the speaker wants to convey that a certain event or situation has

not been seen by others. 'Nannte' means 'such a thing', indicating that it is not something important. 'Minna mite imasen kara' means 'no one see such a thing', emphasizing that the event or situation has not been seen by others.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of negation

sharing of reassurance

explanation of situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of negation

expression of reassurance sharing

expression of situation explanation

One of the reasons I started ...

はじめ りゆう
始めた理由のひとつとしては、

... hajimeta riyuu no hitotsu to shite wa,

One of the reasons I started ...

Variants

- 始めた理由のひとつとしては、興味があったからです。
One of the reasons I started was that I was interested.
- 始めた理由のひとつとしては、挑戦してみたかったからです。
One of the reasons I started was that I wanted to try taking on a challenge.
- 始めた理由のひとつとしては、自分でも試してみたかったからです。
One of the reasons I started was that I wanted to try it myself.

Adjusted Expression

はじめ りゆう
始めた理由のひとつは、興味があったからです。

One of the reasons I started was that I was interested.

Example

このプロジェクトを始めた理由のひとつとしては、新しいことに挑戦してみたかったからです。

One of the reasons I started this project was that I wanted to try taking on something new.

Notes

"One of the reasons I started ..." is used when the speaker explains why they began an action or project by selecting one reason among several possible reasons. By saying "one of the reasons," the speaker shows that this is not the only reason and avoids making the explanation too absolute. "Toshite wa" presents the reason as one candidate or aspect to be taken up. The expression is useful in self-introductions, explanations of activities, and accounts of motivation for research or creative work.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presentation of a reason explanation of motivation introduction to an explanation

limiting the reason to one among others

Tags EN

immediate grammar explanatory expression expression of presenting a reason

expression of explaining motivation conversation-introducing expression

You came at just the right time.

ちょうど、いいところに^き来た。

choudo, ii tokoro ni kita.

You came at just the right time.

Variants

- ちょうど、いいところに来てくれたね。
You came at just the right time, thank you.
- ちょうど、いいところに来てくれてありがとう。
You came at just the right time, I appreciate it.
- ちょうど、いいところに来てくれて助かったよ。
You came at just the right time, it was a great help.

Adjusted Expression

ちょうど、いいところに^き来ましたね。

Thank you for coming at just the right time.

Example

A 「ちょうど、いいところに来たね」 B 「そう？手^て伝^だおうか？」 A 「うん、ありがとう」

A: You came at just the right time. B: Really? Do you want me to help? A: Yes, thank you.

Notes

'Choudo, ii tokoro ni kita ne.' is a colloquial expression where 'choudo' means 'just', indicating that a certain situation or timing is very appropriate. It is often used when the situation may be good for the speaker but may not be good for the person being spoken to.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of welcome

sharing of gratitude

explanation of situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of welcome

expression of gratitude sharing

expression of situation explanation

It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but...

きゅう き
急にこんなこと聞くのも、あれ、なん
だけど、...

kyuu ni konna koto kiku no mo, are, nan da kedo, ...

It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but...

Variants

- 急にこんなこと聞くのも、あれ、なんだけど、ちょっと聞いてもいい？
It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but can I ask you something?
- 急にこんなこと聞くのも、あれ、なんだけど、ちょっと質問してもいい？
It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but can I ask you a question?
- 急にこんなこと聞くのも、あれ、なんだけど、ちょっと相談してもいい？
It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but can I talk to you about something?

Adjusted Expression

とつぜん き きょうしゆく
突然このようなことをお聞きして恐縮ですが、...

I am sorry to ask something like this so suddenly, but...

Example

A 「急にこんなこと聞くのも、あれ、なんだけど、それって事実？」 B 「うん、たぶんそうだと思う」

A: It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but is that true? B: Yes, I think it probably is.

Notes

"It's a bit awkward to ask this suddenly, but..." is used before asking a sudden or somewhat delicate question. "Kyu ni konna koto kiku no mo" first acknowledges that the question may be abrupt. "Are" does not point to a specific object. It loosely indicates something like awkwardness, possible rudeness, or difficulty in saying the question directly. By ending with "nan da kedo," the speaker leaves room for the listener to accept the question before it is asked. The expression is more casual than a formal apology, but it still shows more consideration than asking without any preface.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

preface to a sudden question

softening of awkwardness

consideration for the listener

introduction to a question or consultation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

preface expression

question-introducing expression

consultation-introducing expression

expression of softening awkwardness

technique of speaking loosely

Could you ...?

...てもらえますか？

... te moraemasu ka?

Could you ...?

Variants

- ...いただけますか？
Could you ...?
- ...てくれますか？
Could you please ...?
- ...てくれると助^{たす}かります。
It would be helpful if you could ...

Adjusted Expression

...いただけますか？

Could you please ...?

Example

この書類^{しよるい}を確認^{かくにん}してもらえますか？

Could you check this document?

Notes

"Could you ...?" is used when the speaker wants the listener to do something. Rather than directly saying "please do it," the expression asks whether the speaker can receive the listener's action as a favor. This makes it a request for cooperation rather than a command. "... te

itadakemasu ka" is more polite, while "... te kuremasu ka" is more casual. "... te kureru to tasukarimasu" presents the request by saying that the speaker would be helped by the listener's action.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of request requesting an action from the listener polite request
request for cooperation

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken request expression polite request expression
expression of requesting cooperation benefactive expression

It's truly enjoyable.

じつ たの
実に楽しい。

jitsu ni tanoshii.

It's truly enjoyable.

Variants

- ほんとう たの 本当に楽しい。

It's really enjoyable.

- たの とても楽しい。

It's very enjoyable.

- たの すごく楽しい。

It's really fun.

Adjusted Expression

ほんとう たの 本当に楽しいですね。

It is truly enjoyable.

Example

A 「この作業、さぎょう こま細かくてたいへん大変じゃない？」 B 「うん、でも、じつ たの実に楽しい」

A: Isn't this work detailed and difficult? B: Yes, but it's truly enjoyable.

Notes

"It's truly enjoyable" is used when the speaker evaluates an activity or situation as enjoyable with a sense of inner appreciation. "Jitsu ni" is close to "really," but it sounds somewhat more settled and reflective than

casual emphasis. It is therefore not simply an excited cry of "This is fun!" Rather, it is suitable when the speaker has experienced something and come to appreciate its value or interest. Without a sentence-final particle, "jitsu ni tanoshii" sounds like the speaker is confirming the evaluation inwardly.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of impression

evaluation of enjoyment

expression of inner appreciation

positive evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

expression of impression

expression of evaluating enjoyment

positive evaluation expression

somewhat formal expression

It might take a little longer.

もうちょっとかかるかな。

mou chotto kakaru kana.

It might take a little longer.

Variants

- もうちょっと^{じかん}時間がかかるかな。
It might take a little more time.
- もうちょっと^{てま}手間がかかるかな。
It might take a little more effort.
- もうちょっと^{じかん}時間^{ひつよう}が必要かな。
It might need a little more time.

Adjusted Expression

もう少し、^{すこ}時間^{じかん}がかかるかもしれません。

It may take a little more time.

Example

A 「この^{ぶろ}プロジェクト^{じえくと}、完了^{かんりょう}までどれくらい^{じかん}時間^{ひつよう}が必要ですか？」 B 「うーん、もうちょっとかかるかな」

A: How much time do we need to finish this project? B: Hmm, it might take a little longer.

Notes

"It might take a little longer" softly presents the outlook that a task or process is not finished yet and will need a bit more time. "Mou chotto" makes the additional amount sound small, but it does not specify exactly how short or long it will be. "Kakaru" indicates that time, effort, or cost is needed, and "kana" avoids a firm assertion. The expression is useful when the speaker needs the listener to wait, but wants to share the situation without stating it too strongly.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presentation of an outlook

sharing that more time is needed

expression of uncertainty

soft explanation to the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of outlook

expression of needing more time

expression of uncertainty

situation-explaining expression

Some people do think that way.

そういうふう^{かんが}に考える^{ひと}人もいるよね。

sou iu fuu ni kangaeru hito mo iru yo ne.

Some people do think that way.

Variants

- そういうふう^{かんが}に考える^{ひと}人もいるね。
Some people do think that way.
- そういう^{かんが}考え^{かた}方^{ひと}の人もいるよ。
There are people who see it that way.
- そういう^{みかた}見^{かた}方^{ひと}をする人もいるよね。
Some people have that kind of view.

Adjusted Expression

そういうふう^{かんが}に考える^{ひと}人もいますね。

There are people who think that way.

Example

A 「^と都会^{かい}より^ち地方^{ほう}の方が^く暮らしやすい^{おも}と思う^{ほんとう}って、本当？」 B 「そういうふう^{かんが}に考える^{ひと}人もいるよね」

A: Is it true that some people think it's easier to live in the countryside than in the city? B: Some people do think that way.

Notes

"Some people do think that way" is used when the speaker responds to an opinion or reported view without deciding whether it is true. The speaker only acknowledges that there are people who think that way.

"Sou iu fuu ni" refers back to the viewpoint or framing just mentioned.

"Hito mo iru" places that view as one possible view among others, rather than treating it as a general truth. "Yo ne" shares this recognition with the listener while avoiding a strong statement of agreement or disagreement.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

non-committal response

acknowledgment that a view exists

response by generalization

reserved response to a reported opinion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

response expression

generalization expression

expression of avoiding commitment

expression of acknowledging existence

We have no choice but to do it, right?

するしかないじゃないですか。

suru shika nai ja nai desu ka.

We have no choice but to do it, right?

Variants

- やるしかないじゃないですか。
We have no choice but to do it, right?
- 行くいしかないじゃないですか。
We have no choice but to go, right?
- 食べるたしかないじゃないですか。
We have no choice but to eat it, right?

Adjusted Expression

するい以外のせんたくし選択肢はありませんよね。

There is no option other than doing it, is there?

Example

まず、先さきにこの問題もんだいを解決かいけつするしかないじゃないですか。

First, we have no choice but to solve this problem, right?

Notes

"We have no choice but to do it, right?" is used when the speaker judges that all other options are closed and only one action remains. "Shika nai" closes off other possibilities and leaves only one action. With "ja nai desu ka," the speaker presents this not merely as a personal judgment, but as

something the listener should also recognize given the situation. The expression therefore does more than explain inevitability. It draws the listener into the same situational judgment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of inevitability

presentation that there is no other option

drawing the listener into shared recognition

presentation of situational judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of inevitability

expression of denying other options

expression of shared recognition

expression of situational judgment

Rather, it's better not to look.

むしろ、^み見^{ほう}ない方がいい。

mushiro, minai hou ga ii.

Rather, it's better not to look.

Variants

- むしろ、^み見^{ほう}ない方がいいですよ。
Rather, it's better not to look.
- むしろ、^み見^{ほう}ない方がいい^{おも}と思います。
Rather, I think it's better not to look.
- むしろ、^み見^{ほう}ない方がいいかもしれません。
Rather, it might be better not to look.

Adjusted Expression

むしろ、^み見^{ほう}ない方が^{おも}よいと思います。

Rather, I think it would be better not to look.

Example

A 「この^{ひんと}ヒント、^み見^{ほう}た方がいい？」 B 「いや、むしろ、^み見^{ほう}ない方がいい。わかんなくなるから」

A: Should I look at this hint? B: No, rather, it's better not to look. It will just make things more confusing.

Notes

"Rather, it's better not to look" is used when the expected choice would be to look, but the speaker advises the opposite. "Mushiro" reverses the judgment that the listener or the situation might naturally suggest.

"Minai hou ga ii" does not simply negate looking. It presents not looking as the better option. The expression is useful when looking at a hint, a result, or a detail would actually make things more confusing or increase anxiety.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reversal of the expected choice

suggestion to avoid an action

presentation of situational judgment

advice to the listener

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

suggestion expression

reversal expression

expression of advice to avoid an action

expression of situational judgment

Isn't that obvious?

あ まえ
当たり前じゃないですか。

atarimae ja nai desu ka.

Isn't that obvious?

Variants

- あ まえ
当たり前じゃない？
Isn't that obvious?
- どうぜん
当然じゃないですか。
Isn't that only natural?
- もちろんですよ。
Of course.

Adjusted Expression

どうぜん おも
当然のことだと思います。

I think it is obvious.

Example

A 「これ、^{さき}先に^{かくにん}確認した方が^{ほう}いいですか？」 B 「^あ当たり前^{まえ}じゃないですか。^{あと}後
^{こま}で困りますよ」

A: Should we check this first? B: Isn't that obvious? We'll be in trouble later.

Notes

"Isn't that obvious?" is used when the speaker feels that something is so expected or self-evident that it should not need to be questioned.

"Atarimae" does not simply mean "natural" here. It means that something is obvious or expected as a matter of common sense, procedure, or judgment in the situation. With "ja nai desu ka," the speaker presents it as something the listener should also recognize. Depending on tone, it can sound like a fairly strong pushback against the listener's question.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of obviousness

response to the listener's doubt

strong confirmation

drawing the listener into shared recognition

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of obviousness

confirmation expression

expression of shared recognition

response expression

What are you going to use it for?

なに つか
何に使うの？

nani ni tsukau no?

What are you going to use it for?

Variants

- なに つか
何に使いますか？

What are you going to use it for?

- なに つか
何に使うんですか？

What do you use it for?

- なに しょう
何に使用するんですか？

What will it be used for?

Adjusted Expression

なに しょう
何に使用しますか？

What will it be used for?

Example

A 「これ、^か借りてもいい？」 B 「え、^{なに つか}何に使うの？」 A 「ちょっと、うどんを
ね」 B 「じゃ、^{ちい ほう}こっちの小さい方がいいよ」

A: Can I borrow this? B: Huh, what are you going to use it for? A: Just for
udon. B: Then this smaller one would be better.

Notes

"What are you going to use it for?" is used when the listener is about to use or borrow some object, and the speaker wants to check its purpose. It is not only a request for information. It can also serve as the entry point for deciding whether to lend it, which one to give, or how to help. "Nani ni" asks about purpose or use, and "tsukau no?" confirms the listener's intended use. The expression is casual and is easy to use in everyday situations with people one is familiar with.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking the use

checking the purpose

checking before lending or borrowing

judging the next response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

question expression

expression of checking use

expression of checking purpose

expression of judging the next response

Can I do it?

やらせて？

yarasete?

Can I do it?

Variants

- やらせてください。
Please let me do it.
- やらせてもらえますか？
Could you let me do it?
- やらせてくれませんか？
Would you let me do it?

Adjusted Expression

私にやらせてください。

Please let me do it.

Example

A 「この仕事、誰か^{だれ}やってくれる？」 B 「私^{わたし}にやらせて？」 A 「いいよ、お願い」

A: Can someone take care of this work? B: Can I do it? A: Sure, please.

Notes

"Can I do it?" is used when the speaker asks for permission to perform the action themselves. It is not a request for the listener to do something. Rather, it is an offer asking the listener to give the speaker that role or

opportunity. Although "yaraseru" is a causative form, in this expression it does not mean forcing someone to do something. It means that the speaker will act with the listener's permission. The short form "yarasete?" is casual and immediate, presenting the speaker's desire to take the action.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

request for permission

expression of wanting to take charge

request for an opportunity

offer from the speaker

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of requesting permission

offer expression

expression of wanting to take charge

expression of requesting an opportunity

Do you want more?

もっとほしい？

motto hoshii?

Do you want more?

Variants

- もっとほしいですか？
Do you want more?
- もう少し^{すこ}いる？
Would you like some more?
- もう少し^{すこ}ほしい？
Do you want a little more?

Adjusted Expression

もう少し^{すこ}いかがですか？

Would you like a little more?

Example

A 「このケーキ、美味しい^{おい}ね」 B 「うん、もっとほしい？まだあるよ」 A 「うん、もうちょっと^た食べたいな」

A: This cake is delicious. B: Yes. Do you want more? There's still some left.

A: Yes, I'd like a little more.

Notes

"Do you want more?" is used to check whether the listener wants an additional amount of the same thing. "Motto" indicates adding to what is

already there, and "hoshii?" directly asks about the listener's desire. The expression is easy to use with food, drinks, play, materials for a task, or anything that can be given in additional amounts. However, it sounds quite direct and familiar, so in more polite situations, "Would you like a little more?" is more appropriate.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking whether the listener wants more

offer of an additional amount

checking the listener's satisfaction

offer in a familiar situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

question expression

expression of offering more

expression of checking desire

offer expression

Colophon

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